

FOODITY

D4.6 FOODITY Impact Interim Report

Prepared by AUSTRALO

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Abstract

This document provides a detailed overview of FOODITY's communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities implemented during the first 18 months of the project, explaining the resources, methods, and platforms used in order to successfully disseminate project activities and successes, and providing quantifiable results.

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
CTA	Call to Action
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IT	Information Technology
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NCP	National Contact Point
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PR	Press Release
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SIA	Social Innovation Actor
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SNSF	Sustainable Food Systems Network
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

The FOODITY project

The main goal of FOODITY is to create a European ecosystem of digital solutions that contributes to a more sustainable and healthy food and nutrition system — respecting citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty.

FOODITY will run a **2M€ pilot development programme for creating 12 data-driven solutions** to demonstrate the potential of data-driven innovation in food and nutrition while guaranteeing the user's full control and ownership over their personal data.

These innovations will provide novel solutions to existing research and technical challenges to achieve the four Food 2030 (the EU's research and innovation policy to build better food systems by 2030) key priorities: (1) Nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets, (2) Food systems supporting a healthy planet, (3) Circularity and resource efficiency, and (4) Innovation and empowering communities.

Participants in the pilot development programme will be selected through two open calls to be launched in the second semester of 2023. Eligible beneficiaries will be research and technology organisations (RTOs) and universities, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), social innovation actors and training organisations.

The programme will provide its beneficiaries with a set of value-added services: from one-to-one mentoring to training on technical, business, and legal matters, as well as technical and financial support (up to 187.500€ per beneficiary) for developing their pilots.

During the next three years (January 2023 - December 2025), the FOODITY consortium, comprised of 7 partners, will join forces to make this a reality.

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Executive Summary

This document serves as an **update and detailed reporting and assessment of FOODITY's strategy and framework for Communication, Dissemination and Engagement**. The original framework was outlined in FOODITY's Impact Master Plan (D4.1), focusing on detailing the corresponding strategies. Now, it's time to review the outreach activities undertaken in the project and evaluate their overall effectiveness and impact.

The document provides a thorough overview of the Communication and Dissemination timeline, tools, and methodology. It includes detailed descriptions of each action taken to:

- Promote the project and its outcomes in public forums such as events, conferences, and webinars, whether as participants or hosts.
- Disseminate project results accurately to target communities as well as the general public, ensuring FOODITY's achievements are understandable and accessible to non-experts.
- Maintain open, active, and engaging communication channels to keep target audiences and stakeholders informed about FOODITY's objectives, work plan, and day-to-day activities.
- Develop and implement the established strategy to achieve FOODITY's exploitation objectives.

The FOODITY consortium considers this plan a living document, reflecting an open, ongoing dialogue with potential users and related networks during the project to be inclusive and ensure the best possible results.

1 Introduction

The current document (D4.6 - FOODITY Impact Interim Report) is part of FOODITY's WP4 – Outreach, sustainability and open calls management, specifically focusing on task T4.1 – Dissemination, Communication and Open Call Promotion.

This report offers a comprehensive **overview of all the significant communication, dissemination, exploitation and engagement activities conducted throughout the project's duration up to this point.** It also presents quantitative data on the performance of our digital platforms, participation in both physical and online events, as well as publications and online articles.

The overall strategy for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation was initially outlined in deliverable D4.1 – FOODITY Impact Master Plan. Therefore, this document builds upon the content of D4.1 to provide a clear update in the form of the project's interim report at M18.

The present deliverable is structured into the following main sections:

- Introduction, the current section, which provides an overview of the document context.
- Dissemination & Communication Strategy, analysing its performance considering the KPIs achieved in the period reported.
- A summary of the stakeholders' engagement through the synergies established.
- A detailed reporting in the Dissemination and Communication activities implemented, considering:
 - the online channels used (social media, website, newsletters, online platforms, repositories, etc), the promotional materials produced (printed and multimedia) as well as publications and blog posts.
 - the events, webinars and workshops either attended and/or (co-)organised.
 - the marketing campaigns launched (Open Calls, innovators, etc)
- The implementation of the FOODITY exploitation and sustainability activities
- Next Steps and Conclusions, which summarises the next actions to be implemented, as well as the main takeaway for those already completed.

2 Dissemination & Communication Strategy: performance review

2.1 FOODITY Communication and Dissemination KPIs

As previously outlined in FOODITY's Impact Master Plan (D4.1), the common goal of the communication and dissemination activities was to build and nurture a community and brand around the project, maximise visibility, and engage with stakeholders to foster dialogue and collect feedback on the project's vision and progress.

In this regard, the timeline followed has been:

- During the first 4 months, the project's visual identity and critical brand assets were created, all communication and dissemination channels set up, and the first mapping of stakeholders completed.
- Up until M12, the focus progressively shifted towards establishing a recognisable presence in all our digital channels, beginning the conversation with related initiatives and working on additional promotional materials and long-form articles to cover the core concepts of the project for a wider audience.
- From M12 to M18, efforts have increased in event participation and publications, as well as brainstorming and updating the engagement strategy for reaching the targeted collectives, such as potential Open Calls applicants.

As of the creation of this deliverable, the main goal is to keep building FOODITY's presence in digital channels, reinforcing its core messages, linking them to the desired results and outcomes of the project.

In these 18 months, the project has managed to consolidate its online presence, with more than **1,600 followers in social media, 2,100 including the newsletter subscribers** (see [Section 3.1.2](#)), keeping a steady stream of weekly content in social media that have had a total of **100,966 impressions**, and publishing **19 blog posts** and **7 Zenodo** entries overall.

This promotional effort has been boosted by increased participation in key events, conferences and webinars.

Of course, all these actions have been supported by a branding identity and a set of promotional materials (see [Section 3.2](#)), both in print (e.g. brochures, posters, business cards, roll-up) and digital form, with **17 edited videos** and around **100 graphical elements and animations** produced, (e.g. short clips, creativities, banners).

A specific effort has been dedicated to the creation of valuable synergies, in order to position the project within the ecosystem (see [Section 2.2](#)).

The detailed list of FOODITY's impact KPIs, together with the updated targets at this point, is shown in the following table. A detailed breakdown of the project's metrics (e.g. website, social media) is provided in the dedicated sections addressing the project's digital channels below.

Table 1. Dissemination KPIs

DISSEMINATION KPIs			
Measure	Indicator	Target	Target M18
Peer-reviewed publications	N° of peer-reviewed scientific articles	2	1 submitted
Awareness publications	N° of publications in articles, blog posts, insight papers, citizen factsheets and others: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 19 blog posts • 3 Press Releases • 1 CORDIS article • 1 PhotoVoice Workshops Photo Book 	30	24
Practice abstracts	N° of practice abstracts developed	50	25
Open Access Research	Downloads of open access materials	> 1000	895 views 317 downloads
Webinars/workshops	No. of Webinars / Workshops to (co-)organise: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 How-to-apply webinars/info sessions (2 per open call): 18 (see Section 3.3.2 Webinars and workshops for details) • 6 Internal workshops to support beneficiaries (3 per open call/ round): 3 (details to be added to D.3.3 Report of the FOODITY programme activities v1) • 6 Events targeting citizen empowerment processes: 6 (see Section 3.3.2 Webinars and workshops for details) 	4 6 6	27
Conferences/ fairs	Participation & presentation of FOODITY at events	30	18

Table 2. Communication KPIs

COMMUNICATION KPIs			
Measure	Indicator	Target	Target M18
E-mail campaigns	Broadcasting messages to a database of contact points: Stakeholders' framework database: 1,300 F6S filtered database messaging: 5,320	>5,000	6,320
1-to-1 meetings (Synergies / collaborations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up collaboration with at least 5 EU-funded projects. (6) • Promote the open calls among 20+ innovation ecosystems. (22) • Create synergies with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3+ EU associations (3) ○ 5+ EU DIHs (3) 	33	34
Project website	> 500 unique visitors/ month (average)	500	416
Open calls platform	Receive over 50 successful applications per call	100	104
Social Media	Focus on Twitter and LinkedIn	2,500	+1,600
Newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop quarterly newsletters (4x3=12): 2 • Contribute to 6 external newsletters: 6 	18	8
Press releases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint press release at M01 • Regular PR through partners 	-	3
Printing/merch.	Distribution of hard copies (brochures, flyers, other paper resources)	>1,500	~500
Infographics and banners	Development of graphic elements	>100	~100
Multimedia	The project will produce at least 3 videos and use clips to have self-explanatory and appealing material for the website / social media	3	17 (3 in conjunction with DRG4FOOD)
Success stories	Highlighting the work of the third parties	-	6

2.2 Stakeholder's Engagement

As indicated in D4.1, during the first months, the project identified the stakeholders to be engaged, detailed in the figure below:

Figure 1. FOODITY Stakeholders Map

As a second step, FOODITY focused on informing and engaging stakeholders via dedicated activities. From general dissemination and communication activities (i.e. events participation, workshops organisation, content creation on the website and social media, etc.) to specific ones, such as mailing campaigns, both of which will be detailed in the following sections.

In the table below, a summary of the activities implemented to inform and engage our stakeholders is presented:

Table 3. Dissemination and Communication engagement activities

ACTIVITY	STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	SCOPE
<p>Synergies with other EU Projects:</p> <p>Contact sister projects, projects participated by common partners, etc</p>	<p>Sister project DRG4FOOD</p> <p>Projects participated by consortium partners, such as SoTecln Factory (F6S), EU4Advice (AUS), SOSfood (Softeam and Jibe), etc..</p> <p>Other EU funded projects in related areas, such as TITAN, FOOD-scalEU, HealthyW8 or RESOURCE.</p>	<p>Close collaboration with DRG4FOOD: Participation in each other's project consortium meetings, project focus groups, podcast episodes, newsletters, holding joint webinars and workshops, creating the #Data4FoodCluster for communication and Dissemination purposes, along with a joint Mastodon account. Also, a member of FOODITY is part of the DRG4FOOD External Ethics Board.</p> <p>Regarding other projects, the synergies have been more related to cross-dissemination in social media as well as Newsletters (SoTecln Factory) participation in their stakeholders board (TITAN), or participation in workshops and events, such as the participation of Sploro in an discussion/event organised by FOOD-scalEU an in a workshop organised by RESOURCE, where FOODITY was presented to their innovators. Also, projects like HealthyW8 have explored the possibility of using the the FOODITY DataU.</p>

ACTIVITY	STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	SCOPE
		<p>In the case of some projects (SOSfood, EU4Advice), the contacts are still in their first steps.</p>
<p>Outreach campaign to engage related targets</p>	<p>The relevant target groups prioritized were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EDIHs, Clusters and European Associations ● Horizon Europe NCPs ● Networks, Platforms, and European initiatives ● Potential applicant entities ● Social Innovation Actors 	<p>Mailing campaign to a 1,300 contacts database, most of it composed by multiplicators that could increase the message outreach by using their own networks (see the cases of associations, accelerators or coworking spaces to their members), as well as the targeted mailing done to 5,320 members of the F6S database.</p> <p>Social media campaign to the ~1.600 followers of the project.</p> <p>As a result, the project was featured on the websites and newsletters or invited to events by a wide range of stakeholders. Information about the project was sent to their networks by different ecosystems players, such as DIHs, EU Associations, National Contact Points, Universities, RTOs, Accelerators, Social Innovation Actors and online networks (LSOS, SFSN, FOOD2030...), among others.</p> <p>See Section 3.1.4 for further detail.</p>
<p>Joint InfoDays, webinars and networking events</p>	<p>FOODITY has participated in several joint webinars with different stakeholders a other EU funded projects.</p> <p>FOODITY has been engaged in agri-food networking events, such as the Smart Agrifood Synergy Days 2023 (participated by 28 projects present, DIHs, etc) or networking activities organised by</p>	<p>See the list of all webinars participated and organised or co-organised by FOODITY with other initiatives in Section 3.3.2. In this case it is worth mentioning the following:</p> <p>A. The joint webinars & workshops organised with DRG4FOOD.</p> <p>B. The participation in webinars organised with the collaboration of</p>

ACTIVITY	STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	SCOPE
	<p>related initiatives, such as the FOOD2030 Networks.</p> <p>These actions helped increase the audience reached and hence, their impact.</p>	<p>entities such as IRIS-EDIH Navarra, EBN, EEN, or the Regional Cooperation Council of Bosnia and Herzegovina, were the FOODITY Open Calls were presented along with other cascade funding projects such as: CORTEX2, NEPHELE, COROB, ICOS, XR2Industry, ICAERUS, etc.</p> <p>See all agri-food related events in the list available in Section 3.3.1.</p>

3 Dissemination and Communication activities implemented

The dissemination and communication activities implemented up to M18 focused on two main aspects:

- Make the results open and available for the stakeholders to facilitate their usage (dissemination activities)
- Promote and increase the visibility of the project activities, achievements, team, etc. (communication activities).

In the following chapter, a description of the central dissemination and communication activities carried out by the project up to M18 is presented, focusing on:

- The online channels used;
- The promotional material created;
- The publications;
- The events/workshops participated/organised;
- The Open Calls campaign.

3.1 Online channels

3.1.1 Project website

The FOODITY website highlights the project's mission, vision, and values, detailing its primary objectives, the pilots it will fund, available opportunities, and key news. It follows the branding elements established at the project's inception and is updated with new information as needed.

Important metrics¹ from the website since March 2023 and until June 2024 (15 months) include: 5.012 users, 7.678 sessions started, and **61.000 views (4.066 average monthly views)**.

¹ Extracted from Google Analytics

Figure 2. FOODITY's website users

The FOODITY website has experienced a significant increase in users in several periods.

Firstly, in **July 2023**, when several activities that were carried out were used as an opportunity to start drawing attention to FOODITY's Open Call #1, which was launched on 5 September. Some of the activities that attracted the most interest during this period:

- On 4 July, an [Open Call pre-launch session](#) was held, together with FOODITY's sister project, DRG4Food, to share the keys to both projects' upcoming funding opportunities ([this LinkedIn post](#) about it had 423 impressions, 116 clicks and a 28.13% clickthrough rate).
- On July 25, the first FOODITY online workshop was held, focused on discussing the potential of citizens' personal data to improve food systems and the challenges associated with its collection, concerning privacy and sovereignty (see one of the most successful social media posts on this subject [here](#), with 284 impressions).
- Information was shared to raise awareness of the need for a shift toward sustainable food systems, linking it to the FOODITY Open Call #1 (see one of the most successful social media posts on this subject [here](#), with 516 impressions).
- The first FOODITY PhotoVoice workshops were held (see one of the most successful social media posts on the Austria workshop [here](#), with 129 impressions).

However, it was the announcement of the launch date of the FOODITY Open Call #1 that had the biggest impact on the increase in the number of users of the website — [the first LinkedIn post about it had 700 impressions](#).

Secondly, **from the end of August to mid-October**, a period when communication efforts were focused on driving as many users as possible to the Open Call #1 website.

Some of the social media posts that generated the most website traffic were those related to the announcement of FOODITY's first Open Call and the first informative webinar at the end of August ([this LinkedIn post](#) had 640 impressions). On 5 September, the posts about the Open Call launch ([this LinkedIn post](#) alone had 716 impressions and 856 video views), as well as different reminders about the Open Call and the informative webinars, and the Open Call for external evaluators.

Finally, we are also aware that there has also been an increase in visits since the second open call was launched on 8 May 2024.

The three **countries** from which most users have visited the website are Turkey, Spain and Italy.

Figure 3. FOODITY's website users per country

The **pages with the most views** in order of relevance are the Open Calls (5.604 views), the Home (3.000 views), and the About (851 views).

New items and sites have been added since the website was launched. For example:

- The [Open Call #1](#) and [Open Call #2, Calls for Evaluators](#) and [Call for Experts](#) sites have been published. These pages can be seen in [Annexes A to D](#).
- As can be seen in [Annex E](#), a specific site has been added to showcase the [materials and resources](#) produced by the project, such as those related to communication, printed. More information on these materials can be found throughout the current deliverable.
- Another page has been added to address more technical parts of the project, such as the one dedicated to the link with the [Datalake platform](#).

Figure 4. FOODITY's Datalake platform

For the project's **Open Calls**, a dedicated page was created, including a general overview and specific sections for [Open Call #1](#) (now closed) and [Open Call #2](#). These sections provide all necessary details for successful applications, such as:

- The objectives
- The offerings to applicants
- The target organizations
- Details on the different topics addressed by the Call
- All supporting documentation for download
- Access to recordings of the informative webinars
- The steps from application to the results phase and the start of the Support Programme
- A helpdesk contact and FAQs section

Similar structure and sections (when applicable) were added to the evaluators and mentors calls (characteristics and how to apply).

Other updates have been made to the website, as needed for the implementation of the project activities. Most updates relate to the [News section](#), where a total of **19 news items** have been published during this period (see more information on the type of content in [Section 3.2.3](#)).

Figure 5. FOODITY's News section

3.1.2 Social media

FOODITY has maintained an active presence on social media platforms such as Twitter (now called X), LinkedIn, and YouTube since its inception, garnering a combined audience of +1,600 followers (around 2,100 including the newsletter subscribers). On average, the project achieved **5,609 post impressions per month**, totaling over **100,960 impressions** and more than **300 posts** created across these platforms. FOODITY uses these channels to promote its progress, activities, results, and opportunities, effectively engaging its stakeholders.

- [LinkedIn](#) is the project's primary social channel, with a community of 879 followers and 56,995 post impressions.
- [Twitter \(now X\)](#) has a community of 684 followers and 34,371 post impressions.
- [YouTube](#) functions as the project's video repository, with 41 subscribers, 17 videos, 1,500 views and 9,600 impressions.

Some of the topics most frequently addressed on the FOODITY social channels include:

- FOODITY Open Calls (including info webinars, matchmaking events, calls for experts and evaluators).
- Project updates, facts, objectives, or highlights.
- #FOODITYopencall1, #FOODITYopencall2, #FOODITYnews, #FOODITYworkshops, #FOODITYteam, #FOODITYinnovators, etc.
- Relevant industry news, events, opportunities, and resources.

FOODITY's most extensive social media campaigns to date have been focused on promoting its first and second open call, aiming to reach as many food and nutrition innovators as possible and encouraging a high number of applications (see full details on the Open Calls Strategy in [Section 3.4](#)).

Part of the campaign also promoted the informative webinars about the calls—encouraging potential applicants to register (via the [FOODITY profile on the F6S platform](#)), attend, and watch the [recordings](#). These have been the official informative webinars held by the consortium:

Open Call #1:

- [Prelaunch webinar: FOODITY & DRG4FOOD funding opportunities: Ask us anything!](#)
- [FOODITY Open Call 1: Webinar 1](#)
- [FOODITY Open Call 1 - Webinar 2](#)

Open Call #2:

- [FOODITY Open Call 2: Info webinar 1](#)
- [DRG4FOOD & FOODITY Matchmaking Event](#)
- FOODITY Open Call 2 - Webinar 2: Why you need citizen engagement to scale your solution

Figure 6. FOODITY's Open Call 2 - Webinar 2

The project partners have also presented the call in external webinars and other platforms, adding up to a total of 18 webinars. Details on these are included in [Section 3.3.2](#).

Many engaging communication materials and visual content were created for this purpose, including a press release, various banners, animations, slide decks, and ready-to-print graphics for physical events. These materials can be found in the [Communications Toolkit for Call #1](#) and [Call #2](#), which were distributed among FOODITY partners and other collaborators to help promote the call by including it on their websites, social media, newsletters, mailings, and other communication channels.

The organic campaign focused on regularly posting about the open calls, emphasising its different aspects—from its topics, the target organisations, and the application process.

Some examples of the social media posts that have been published:

Figure 7. FOODITY's Open Calls – example of social media posts

Overall, the Open Call #1 communication campaign was a great success, attracting a high number of applications — with 104 submitted (and more than 150 non-finalised applications), coming from +30 different countries. Regarding the Open Call #2, to be closed on July 10 2024, at the moment of writing this report, 92 applications have been started with 9 already finalised.

3.1.3 Newsletters

The [first FOODITY newsletter](#) was published in August 2023, focused on announcing the official launch date of the Open Call #1, both on Brevo and LinkedIn, which have 207 and 301 subscribers, respectively — 508 in total.

This number included information such as:

- The announcement of the Open Call #1 launch
- The pre-launch session held with FOODITY's sister project DRG4FOOD
- A “meet the team” article presenting the consortium members and their role

The [second number of the project newsletter](#), published on May 2024, was focused on announcing the launch of Open Call #2 and informing about the milestones and news coming from the project activities, such as:

- The results of Open Call #1 and presentation of the winners
- The different opportunities for the parties interested in participating in Open Call #2 to get information about the application process.

Figure 8. FOODITY's Newsletter N°2

The next editions of the newsletter will be focused on highlighting different aspects of the project's achievements, such as the evolution of the 1st round of pilots funded, the presentation of the 2nd batch, the scientific production of FOODITY and other news and milestones.

FOODITY has also been featured in **6 external newsletters**:

- From other EU projects like [DRG4FOOD](#), sister project of FOODITY, or [SoTeIn Factory](#).

<p>DRG4FOOD & FOODITY matchmaking event</p> <p>Foodity & DRG4FOOD joint matchmaking event was held on May 23rd. By creating a space to network researchers, startups and SMEs, we help find potential partners for both projects' open calls.</p> <p>See more</p>	
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Figure 9. FOODITY featured in the DRG4FOOD Newsletters #2 and #3

Explore other social innovation programmes and opportunities	
<p>REshaping Supply CHAins for Positive social Impact</p> <p>ReShape</p>	
<p>FOODITY launches open call 2 to fund data-driven solutions for food and nutrition</p> <p>The EU-funded project FOODITY will fund six data-driven solutions to boost innovation in food and nutrition while putting the power of personal data use back into the hands of citizens.</p> <p>FOODITY's €1M pilot development program will provide up to €187,500, mentoring, training, and technical support to beneficiaries over 12 months.</p> <p>Apply until 10 July 2024: https://foodity.eu/open-call-2/</p>	<p>Meet ReShape - EU funded project reshaping supply chains for positive social impact</p> <p>The 3-year project aims to analyse social, economic, and environmental changes, including the COVID-19 pandemic, and their impact on supply chains.</p> <p>ReShape will study innovative supply chain models to streamline processes and prioritize humans with the help of digital technologies. The results will include policy scenarios and recommendations to support sustainability and resilience in supply chains.</p> <p>Check out ReShape website</p>

Figure 10. FOODITY featured in the SoTecin Factory Newsletter #6

- Newsletters from different stakeholders such as:
 - HE Tubitak newsletters (Horizon Europe National Contact Point for Digital and Space), sent to its 9K subscribers and also published the FOODITY Open Call in their [website](#).
 - The [Sustainable Food Systems Network](#) (SNSF) Community Managers newsletter.

FEATURED NEWS FROM THE NETWORK

Interested in food systems transformation in a local community context? Then the Food, Place & Innovation Summer School might be something for you! Read more about it [here](#).

Do you work with food waste? University of Reading is looking for experts to identify knowledge gaps and empower stakeholders to reduce food loss. Check the survey [here](#).

Wanted: guest expert speaker on food systems & citizen engagement. The event is the 18th of June. Read more in [this post](#) by the project FOODITY.

Figure 11. FOODITY featured in the SFSN Community Managers weekly newsletter

- The [LSOS Collaboration Platform](#) Report
- The [Impact Hub](#) Global newsletter

LSOS Collaboration Platform Report

Summary of the latest content according to personal interests:

Browse new requests, you could be a match.

AUSTRALO

Solution Request (RFP)

FOODITY Open Call #1 - Up to €187,500 for data-driven solutions to boost innovation in food and nutrition

#Nutrition & New Food #Food & Consumer Goods

[Browse through all requests](#)

Do you have the next big digital idea to empower citizens towards better food choices and more sustainable food systems?

Apply to FOODITY Open Call #2

Deadline: 10 July 2024

Foodity | Food and nutrition innovation funding opportunities

FOODITY is now accepting applications for its second open call, aiming to fund six innovative, data-driven solutions in food and nutrition with a total of €1M. Selected participants will receive up to €187,500, along with mentoring, training, and technical support to develop their projects over 12 months. [Apply before 10 July 2024.](#)

Figure 12. FOODITY featured in the LSOS Collaboration Platform Report and the Impact Hub Global Newsletter

Finally, the FOODITY partners have also included information about the project and its open calls in their own communication channels, from their social media to their websites. They have also created entries in their blogs or, for the purpose of this section, in their newsletters. Such is the case of several numbers of the [AUSTRALO newsletter](#), [Sploro](#) or [CERTH](#), among others.

3.1.4 Online Platforms and other actors

Sustainable Food Systems Network:

- 2,404 total members in general group
- Up until now, 8 posts have been published about FOODITY (5 ours, 3 DRG4Food) with 2,776 views.
- This platform hosts the [online FOOD 2030 Networks](#), with 393 members, being FOODITY one of them, and participating in the events and discussions organised by the Network in this forum.

Figure 13. FOODITY featured in the Sustainable Food Systems Network

The project has also been featured by many stakeholders in their websites, or shared the Open Calls and opportunities to their relevant contacts through email, as well as invited FOODITY to their events and other types of exchanges.

Examples of these are the interactions with the following **stakeholders**:

- **At least 3 European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH)** such as SmartAgrihubs, with the participation of several FOODITY partners in their [2023 Synergy days](#), the IRIS DIH Navarra, that invited the project to present Open Call #2 at an [online cascade funding webinar](#), or the GreenSupplyChain Digital Innovation Hub (Greece), which shared the project among its networks.

- **3 EU Associations and Networks**, such as the FOOD2030 Networks, that [published Open Call #2 in their website](#), the [Enterprise Europe Networks Agrifood, Health, and Digital Sector Groups](#) and the [European Business Network](#) which invited the project to participate in online webinars.
- **9 Innovation organisations and RTOs (many of them Horizon Europe NCPs):**
 - Austrian Research Promotion Agency, European and International Programmes
 - Research Foundation Flanders
 - Danish Agency for Higher Education & Science (under the Ministry of Higher Education and Science)
 - National Research Development & Innovation Office, Department for International Affairs - Hungary
 - Malta Council for Science and Technology
 - Information Technologies Institute, Visual Computing Laboratory - Greece
 - National Centre for Research and Development - Poland
 - Fund for Innovation and Technological Development - North Macedonia
 - Dotaceu.cz - National Coordination Authority, Ministry of Regional Development CZ
- **6 Accelerators and organisations supporting entrepreneurs**, such as [CEEIM](#) (Centro de Empresas e Innovación de Murcia), that invited the project to present Open Call #2 at an [online cascade funding webinar](#), Impact Hub Lisbon (dissemination of the Call to their members), Impact Hub Madrid and Impact Hub Global (which have already or will include the project in their newsletters), [Impact Shakers](#), [Athens Tech Circle](#), as well as the Netherlands Enterprise Agency or Enterprise Ireland, which have also shared the project opportunities to their members.
- **2 Universities** that have disseminated the FOODITY Open Calls through their networks:
 - University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics - Bosnia and Herzegovina
 - University Donja Gorica - Montenegro
- **5 Online platforms for the dissemination of EU projects and funding opportunities**, such as [eufundingportal.eu](#), [Guía Financiación Comunitaria](#), [Developmentaid.org](#), [Getonepass.eu](#), [Considered Capital](#), that have included the FOODITY Open Calls.

3.1.5 Zenodo

Following the European Commission guidelines for Open Science, FOODITY provides open access to peer-reviewed publications, public deliverables, brand assets, and other resources generated within the project.

A dedicated [Zenodo FOODITY community](#) and repository is already in place for the project, where publications, press releases, and more can be found. Public deliverables will be uploaded to Zenodo and to our website once validated by the European Commission.

Thanks to the promotional strategy set up to make the project's results available to our stakeholders, we have achieved over 317 downloads and 895 views for the 7 documents uploaded to the FOODITY Zenodo community, including:

- Communication and Dissemination materials, such as the official project logo, the launch press release and the Open Calls press releases.
- The 1st and 2nd newsletters.
- The FOODITY PhotoVoice Workshops Photo Book.

Figure 14. FOODITY's Zenodo Community

3.2 Promotional Materials

3.2.1 Printed Material

Regarding **ready to print materials**, the following were created:

- One-Pager (generic)
- One-Pager (per Open Call)
- Roll-Up (to display during conferences and events - several versions)
- Business Cards (ready to print & online)

Also, **other promotional materials have been developed ad hoc**, depending on the needs of the project and the consortium demands. For example, the ones specifically made for our PhotoVoice workshops and citizen dialogues, such as:

- Invitation templates
- Participation certificate templates
- Roll-up templates
- Flyer templates
- Business card template
- PhotoVoice workshop photo book

Figure 15. Examples of ready to print promotional materials

3.2.2 Multimedia Material

Regarding the multimedia materials produced, we can divide them between general materials and videos:

General:

- Logo
- Branding elements
- Banners
- SoMe templates
- Slide decks

- Zoom backgrounds
- QR codes
- Visuals and animations

Videos, divided into the following themes (topic and number):

- #FOODITYteam interviews (2)
- #FOODITYinnovators (7)
- #FOODITYopencall1 (1)
- #FOODITYopencall2 (2)
- Webinar recordings (5):
 - Open call #1 (3)
 - Open call #2 (2)

Figure 16. FOODITY's produced videos

Open Call #1 & Open Call #2 Communication and Dissemination Toolkits (See Annex F):

- Press Releases
- Sample texts for SoMe, emails and newsletters
- Visuals

- Flyers
- Animations
- Links to webinars, etc.

3.2.3 Publications

Awareness publications

A total of **19 blog posts** have been produced, detailing different highlights of the project, such as:

The participation in events, webinars, workshops and meetings:

- [Introducing FOODITY: Pioneering data-driven solutions for healthy and sustainable food systems](#)
- [FOODITY kickoff meeting: Setting the stage for data-driven innovation](#)
- [FOODITY & DRG4FOOD funding opportunities: Ask us anything!](#)
- [FOODITY workshop: Empowering citizens to improve food systems](#)
- [\[Video\] FOODITY & DRG4FOOD funding opportunities: Ask us anything!](#)
- [Workshop on data, privacy, and food systems: Building trust and collaboration](#)
- [Food for Thought: The EU Food 2030 Pathways Data Strategy for the Food System](#)
- [FOODITY & DRG4FOOD joint matchmaking event for startups, SMEs and researchers](#)
- [FOODITY Open Call 2: Webinar 1](#)

Interviews

- [Meet the coordinator behind FOODITY: Samuel Almeida, EU projects manager at F6S](#)

Innovators Showcase

- [Meet the Innovators From FOODITY Open Call 1](#)
- [Meet the FOODITY innovators: CSE-TKAS, The Kitchen Adventure](#)
- [Meet the FOODITY innovators: FoodMarketMap](#)
- [Meet the FOODITY innovators: DIAITA](#)

PhotoVoice Workshops

- [Conclusions from the PhotoVoice Workshop Organized by Jibe Company in Sofia](#)
- [Exploring Personal Data Management in the F6S-Organized PhotoVoice Workshop in Coimbra](#)
- [Insights from ZSI's PhotoVoice Workshop on Food and Nutrition Data](#)

Citizen Dialogues

- [FOODITY Citizen Dialogues: Plovdiv Food Fest 2024](#)

Announcements and milestones

- [Results of the FOODITY Open Call #1](#)

3 Press Releases have been produced, for press distribution as well as accompanying email campaigns:

- [FOODITY Open Call #1 Launch Press Release](#)
- [FOODITY Open Call #2 Launch Press Release](#)
- [FOODITY Project Launch Press Release](#)

Another awareness article was published on the [News & Multimedia](#) section of [CORDIS](#), where the social media channels have been added to the project profile.

Figure 17. FOODITY's CORDIS profile

The project has also published the [FOODITY PhotoVoice Workshops Photo Book](#), which is available in Zenodo for view or/and download, as well as [on the website](#) in its English version.

This Photo Book is a very visual document that explains and tries to facilitate the understanding of the results and key insights that emerged from the three FOODITY workshops. These workshops were hosted in the summer of 2023 by the Austrian, Bulgarian and Portuguese hubs, and discussed with the citizens their perception of data privacy and data sovereignty linked to food and nutrition. The Photo Book was also translated into the hub languages.

Figure 18. PhotoVoice Workshops Photo Book

Lastly, and regarding **Scientific publications**, CERTH has submitted a paper to the [Nutrients \(MDPI\) Journal](#):

- Paper title: Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning technologies for Personalized and Precision Nutrition: A Systematic Review.
- At the moment of writing this report the paper is under the second round of review.

Header (First Page) ▾

Review

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning technologies for Personalized and Precision Nutrition: A Systematic Review

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Abstract: Modern lifestyle trends, such as sedentary behaviour and unhealthy diets, have been associated with obesity, a major health challenge increasing the risk of multiple pathologies. This has prompted many to reassess their routines and seek expert guidance on healthy living. In the digital era, users quickly turned to mobile apps for support. These apps monitor various aspects of daily life, such as physical activity and calorie intake, collect extensive user data, and apply modern data-driven technologies, including Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), to provide personalised diet and lifestyle recommendations. This work examines the state of the art in data-driven technologies for personalised nutrition, including relevant data collection technologies, and explores the research challenges in this field. A systematic literature review, following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guideline, was conducted using three databases, covering studies from 2021 to 2024, resulting in 67 final studies. The data are presented in separate subsections for recommendation systems and data collection technologies, with a discussion section identifying research challenges. The findings indicate that the fields of data-driven innovation and personalised nutrition are predominately amalgamated in the use of recommender systems.

Figure 19. Abstract of the paper submitted by CERTH to the Nutrients (MDPI) Journal

3.3 Events

3.3.1 Events

FOODITY has been featured in **18 conferences and other type of events** up to month 18 of the project, with participation of a **total audience of more than 150,000 people** among a wide range of stakeholders, such as SMEs and startups, research and technical organisations, ecosystem players (EU initiatives, clusters, EDIHs and related projects), theme relevant events, etc.

Table 4. FOODITY's participation in events and conferences

EVENTS AND CONFERENCES ATTENDED UP TO M18					
Type	Event	Date	Description	Location	Partner
Conference	South Summit	07/06/2023	Promotional activities and applicants scouting	Madrid, Spain	Sploro
Conference	Digital Enterprise Show	13/06/2023	Promotional activities and applicants scouting	Málaga, Spain	Sploro
Conference	Webit 2023	28/06/2023	Attendance to Webit 2023 to promote the Open Calls	Sofia, Bulgaria	F6S
Online event	FOOD-scalEUp - FOLLOW UP: Acceleration programs peer-to-peer group discussion	12/09/2023	Event prepared by the Food-scalEUp project to hold a discussion on important aspects of internationalisation and the needs of food companies	Online	Sploro
Conference	Infoday and Brokerage event in Cluster 6	26-27/9/2023	Infoday and brokerage event for Cluster 6 topics with direct meetings with potential candidates for the FOODITY open call	Brussels, Belgium	Sploro

EVENTS AND CONFERENCES ATTENDED UP TO M18					
Type	Event	Date	Description	Location	Partner
Conference	FOOD TECH & nouvelles technologies - Conférences	27/09/2023	Systematic, in partnership with the City of Antony, proposes to take an inventory of new technologies in the Food Tech sector, to contribute to a more sustainable and secure use of the resources offered to us by our planet. The objective is twofold: meet the food needs of tomorrow & innovate to succeed in the agro-ecological transition.	France	Softeam
Conference	Synergy days Smart Agrihubs	04/10/2023	The Synergy Days is the most important conference connecting the digital innovators of the European agri-food sector. 28 projects present / DIHs, etc.	Thessaloniki Greece	Sploro CERTH
Online Event	Enterprise Europe Networks Agrifood, Health, and Digital Sector Groups	24/10/2023	Promotion of OC#1 alongside DRG4FOOD at EEN SG event.	Online	F6S
Online Event	EU Funding Clinics: Cascade Funding Opportunities AgriFood	25/10/2023	EU Funding Clinics: Cascade Funding Opportunities AgriFood -- OC#1 promotion	Online	F6S
Conference	European FoodSafety4EU forum	28-29/11/2023	The EU Food Safety Forum is the new Science-Policy-Society interface, an open space for discussion and collaboration as a periodic appointment for institutions, Food Safety Authorities, European and national Agencies, universities and research centers, companies, enterprises, consumers and umbrella associations.	Brussels, Belgium	ZSI

EVENTS AND CONFERENCES ATTENDED UP TO M18					
Type	Event	Date	Description	Location	Partner
Online Event	Food for thought session: "The EU FOOD 2030 pathways strategy and how data will make our food system more sustainable"	09/02/2024	Joint session between the EC, Sustainability Consortium, Foodity and DRG4Food	Online	F6S/Sploro
Conference	Mobile World Congress	26/02/2024	Promotional activities and applicants scouting	Barcelona, Spain	Sploro
Conference	FOOD 2030 Networks Conference	5-7/03/2024	Coordinate cross-project collaboration on common objectives for transforming the agriculture and food system through policy, innovation, business development, education, public engagement, dissemination and communication.	Hybrid	F6S
Conference	European Innovation Council Summit	18/03/2024	Promotional activities and applicants scouting	Brussels, Belgium	Sploro
Conference	Plovdiv Food Park Festival 2024	30/05-02/06/2024	Promotional activities and applicants scouting. FOODITY had a specific booth where the citizen dialogues surveys were distributed among the attendees to the event	Bulgaria	Jibe
Conference	PODIM	13/05/2024	Annual conference in Europe that focuses on startups, innovation, and entrepreneurship. It brings together entrepreneurs, investors, corporate executives, and other stakeholders from the startup ecosystem to share knowledge, network, and explore opportunities.	Maribor, Slovenia	Sploro

EVENTS AND CONFERENCES ATTENDED UP TO M18					
Type	Event	Date	Description	Location	Partner
Event	The future of FOOD 2030 Networks: networking & new features!	19/06/2024	Networking with other FOOD 2030 Network projects using Zoom's breakout rooms (participation in the Comms and Diss subgroup)	Online	AUS
Conference	11th European Urban Resilience Forum - #EURESFO24	26-28/6/2024	Showcase of FOODITY in the Marketplace arena of the conference, Stand19	Valencia, Spain	F6S

3.3.2 Webinars and workshops

FOODITY has organised, co-organised or participated in **18 webinars and workshops** during the reported period, with a total of **more than 764 attendees (average of ~42 per webinar)** among its target audience in regard to the developments of the project, especially potential applicants to the Open Calls #1 and #2, as well as both Calls for Evaluators and a Call for Experts.

Table 5. FOODITY's participation in webinars and workshops

WEBINARS AND WORKSHOPS ATTENDED UP TO M18					
Type	Event	Date	Description	Location	Partner
Webinar	Why we need a trustworthy data-driven food system	04/05/2023	Webinar organised by the DRG4FOOD project about their project. FOODITY will have a short presentation about its project.	Online	F6S, SOFT
Webinar	Cascade Funding Opportunities - Camara de Comercio de Alava	01/06/2023	Webinar aimed at introducing the concept of cascade funding and presenting Sploro's initiatives, including FOODITY	Online	Sploro

WEBINARS AND WORKSHOPS ATTENDED UP TO M18					
Type	Event	Date	Description	Location	Partner
Webinar	FOODITY & DRG4FOOD funding opportunities: Ask us anything!	04/07/2023	Pre-launch open calls webinar organised by FOODITY and DRG4FOOD	Online	F6S
Workshop	Common Online Workshop for the FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network	20/09/2023	FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network the CLEVERFOOD project is bringing together EU-funded projects, partnerships and networks that are working on transforming the European food system.	Online	F6S, SOFT
Workshop	DRG4FOOD Focus Group	21/09/2023	Participation in the focus group to help define challenges to address in the OC and network	Brussels, Belgium	F6S
Webinar	EIT Food TeamUp 2023 programme	27/09/2023	Webinar aimed at introducing the concept of cascade funding and presenting Sploro's initiatives, including FOODITY. The audience are 15 food-related startups that have been selected in the EIT Food TeamUp programme	Online	Sploro
Webinar	DRG4FOOD OC#1	12/10/2023	Promotion of OC#1 during DRG4FOOD's OC#1 webinar	Online	F6S
Webinar	Sploro Cascade Funding Webinar Series - Agriculture and Food Technology	31/10/2023	Presentation FOODITY Open Call #1	Online	F6S/Sploro

WEBINARS AND WORKSHOPS ATTENDED UP TO M18					
Type	Event	Date	Description	Location	Partner
Workshop	INEO Start Workshop	18/04/2024	Presentation of the FOODITY Open Call #2 to a selection of startups as part of a INEO Start workshop	Coimbra, Portugal	F6S
Webinar	FOODITY OC2 Webinar #1	16/05/2024	Regular info webinar for Open Call #2	Online	F6S
Webinar	Online Cascade Funding Infowebinar for Regional Cooperation Council - Bosnia and Herzegovina	23/05/2024	FOODITY project presentation + OC #2 & evaluators calls	Online	AUS
Webinar	DRG4FOOD & FOODITY Matchmaking	23/05/2024	Pitching opportunity for entities seeking partners for both OCs	Online	F6S/AUS
Webinar	Sploro CascadeFunding Webinar Series	27/05/2024	Info sessions about different OCs happening including FOODITY Open Call #2	Online	F6S/Sploro
Webinar	EBN EU Project Pill #1 Cascade Funding Opportunities	29/05/2024	Organised in collaboration with the EU BIC Associate Sploro, this EU Project Pill will focus on cascade funding opportunities available in the three priority areas identified by the European Business and Innovation Centre Network in 2024: circular economy, deep tech and open innovation.	Online	Sploro
Workshop	Resource Project Workshop	05/06/2024	Workshop on cascading finance to a group of nine startups. As the scope of the companies attending was the circular economy, among other funding opportunities, we provided an overview of the Foodity project, as well as the conditions for	Zaragoza, Spain	Sploro

WEBINARS AND WORKSHOPS ATTENDED UP TO M18					
Type	Event	Date	Description	Location	Partner
			participation. The general workshop was followed by individual mentoring sessions with the startups.		
Webinar	DRG4FOOD OC#2	06/06/2024	Promotion of OC#2 during DRG4FOOD's OC#2 webinar.	Online	F6S
Webinar	FOODITY OC2 Interactive Citizen Engagement Session	18/06/2024	Interactive session with potential applications on the importance of Citizen Engagement in FOODITY and more generally for scaling.	Online	F6S/ CSE/ ZSI
Webinar	IRIS POLE - EDIH of Navarra	19/06/2024	Presentation FOODITY opportunities	Online	AUS

The FOODITY consortium has organised **two types of interactive workshops geared towards gathering the insights and engagement of the citizens** to include their feedback in the project activities:

- **PhotoVoice Workshops: three workshops in Austria, Portugal and Bulgaria** were organised to gather the opinion of a diverse group of citizens on data privacy and sovereignty in food and nutrition. They have also allowed participants to learn how having better control of their personal data can lead to a healthier, more sustainable lifestyle.
- **Citizen Dialogues:** two Citizen Dialogue events were organised during the period reported, one of them hosted by Jibe in the Bulgarian hub, and held in the framework of the Plovdiv Food Park Festival in 2024, where a specific booth were more than a hundred surveys were distributed and answered by the attendees to the event. Also, another Citizen Dialogue event was hosted by F6S by the Portuguese hub, in June 2024, in the format of an interactive discussion throughout lunch, with 42 participants attending. The last Citizen Dialogue, to be organised by the Austrian hub, will happen in the fall and it is currently being organised.

Another kind of interactive activity was the **Stakeholders workshop**, held online on July 2023 and moderated by ZSI. During this online event, the goal was, along with the validation and complementation of literature as well as the results of the stakeholders' interviews, the introduction of the project and its open calls and then a brainstorming session in order to collect and formulate first ideas for solutions.

Table 6. FOODITY's internal workshops

INTERNAL WORKSHOPS ORGANISED BY THE FOODITY PARTNERS TO M18					
Type	Event	Date	Description	Location	Partner
Workshop	Bulgaria Hub PhotoVoice Workshop	03/07/2023	The FOODITY partner Jibe, hosted an interactive PhotoVoice workshop in Sofia, Bulgaria. This interactive PhotoVoice workshop provided an opportunity for a diverse group of individuals to explore and express their perspectives on the use of personal health and nutrition data.	Sofia, Bulgaria	JIBE
Workshop	Austria Hub PhotoVoice Workshop	03/07/2023	The FOODITY partner ZSI hosted an insightful PhotoVoice workshop in Vienna, Austria, where participants from diverse backgrounds delved into the intricate realm of food and nutrition data. Spanning ages 21 to 60 and representing a balanced mix of genders, the group offered a kaleidoscope of perspectives.	Vienna, Austria	ZSI
Workshop	FOODITY stakeholder workshop	25/07/2023	European stakeholders discussed cutting-edge research findings and exchanged insights and experiences regarding food and nutrition data within the context of citizen data sovereignty.	Online	ZSI
Workshop	Portugal Hub PhotoVoice Workshop	23/09/2023	Organisation of the Portugal Hub PhotoVoice workshop	Porto, Portugal	F6S

INTERNAL WORKSHOPS ORGANISED BY THE FOODITY PARTNERS TO M18					
Type	Event	Date	Description	Location	Partner
Workshop	Bulgarian hub Citizen Dialogues activity: in the framework of the Plovdiv Food Park Festival 2024	30/05-02/06/2024	The citizen dialogues surveys were distributed among the attendees to the event and more than 100 were answered by the participants	Bulgaria	JIBE
Workshop	Portugal hub Citizen Dialogue activity: FOODITY Lunch Talk	21/06/2024	Organisation of a Citizen Dialogue event (Task 5.3) in the format of an interactive discussion throughout lunch (42 participants)	Porto, Portugal	F6S

The project has also participated in two of the events of DRG4FOOD, to discuss potential collaboration and their status, such as:

- The [DRG4FOOD Kick off Meeting](#), held in Brussels, 18-19th January 2023.
- The DRG4FOOD Consortium Meeting held online on 16 November 2023, where FOODITY participated as a guest speaker.

On the other hand, DRG4FOOD's coordinator was also present in the [FOODITY Kick-off meeting](#), held in Porto, on 1 and 2 February 2023.

All the events and activities described in this section were properly announced and communicated through the project and partners' channels. See hereunder some examples of social media posts regarding the participation of FOODITY in events, conferences, webinars and workshops:

FOODITY
859 followers
1mo • Edited • 🌐

#SaveTheDate 📅 Calling innovative startups, SMEs and researchers eager to make a positive impact on food systems: Register for the joint **#matchmaking** event we have organised with our sister project, **#DRG4FOOD!**

This is an excellent opportunity to present your project and connect with industry experts and potential partners to apply to our upcoming **#OpenCalls**.

Be quick! If you're among the first 10 registrants, you'll have the chance to **#pitch** your ideas and **#network** during the session.

📅 Tuesday, 23 May 2024
🕒 15:00 - 16:30 (CET)
🔗 Register now: <https://lnkd.in/d9Pm5c4j>

#Data4FoodCluster | **SciFoodHealth** European Food Information Council (EUFIC) | **Nika Levikov Maja Fišić**

Save the date!
📅 23 May 2024
📍 15:00 - 16:30 (CET)
🔗 Register now: <https://lnkd.in/d9Pm5c4j>

Register now
foodity.eu

FOODITY
859 followers
2d • 🌐

Our Open Call 2 **#InfoDays** continue! 📅 Today, our colleague **Raquel Carro (AUSTRALO)** will present it on a webinar hosted by **IRIS Navarra, Polo de Innovación Digital**, with the EU-funded projects **CORTEX2, NEPELE** and **COROB Project**.

🔗 Join us at 9:30 am CET here: <https://lnkd.in/egUZbvXJ>

#IRISEDIH #CascadeFunding FundingBox Graciela Garrido Antonio Salvador Calvo Econet Consultants (FundingBox Group)

IRIS NAVARRA EUROPEAN INNOVATION HUB

CASCADE FUNDING CALLS PRESENTATION DAY

Webinar | 19 June 2024 Online (Zoom)

Presentation of Cascade Funding opportunities: **COROB, NEPELE, CORTEX2** and Foodity

COROB **nephele** **CORTEX2** **FOODITY**

FOODITY
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📅 Join us TODAY to learn the keys to preparing a winning proposal for our open call (offering up to €187K + mentoring + training to food innovators) and learn how citizen engagement can scale your innovative solution!

🌟 We'll be joined by a very inspiring guest: **László Jaczenkó, Climate Smart Elephant** Co-Founder and part of **#CSETKAS**, one of the teams selected in our Open Call 1.

He'll share his experience in our Pilot Development Programme and explain the importance of citizen and end-user engagement in boosting products and services.

From our **#FOODITYteam**, we'll be joined by **Nika Levikov**, EU Projects Manager at **F6S**, and **Maria Schrammel**, Project Manager and Researcher at the **Centre for Social Innovation**.

🔗 If you haven't registered yet, here's your last chance to do so: https://lnkd.in/dHPvhQ_D

#FOODITYopencall2 | F6S Innovation

FOODITY Open Call #2 Webinar #2

Why you need citizen engagement to scale your solution

18 June 2024 - 3:00 pm CET

Last chance to register!

🇪🇺 Funded by the European Union **FOODITY**

Figure 20. FOODITY events and webinars/workshops participation

3.4 Open Calls Campaign

The **Open Calls Campaigns Strategy** explained in this section, entails a series of actions conducted before, during, and after Open Call #1, as well as Open Call #2 (this one with the improvements added from the learnings gathered during the Open Call #1 Campaign).

The following list includes the to-dos for Open Call #2 in regards to the “before” and “during” activities (the most updated version) as well as the Evaluators Call #2.

In the case of the “after” to-dos, these correspond to the Open Call #1.

A similar strategy was followed for the Experts Campaign.

3.4.1 Before the Open Calls (Open Call #2)

Table 7. FOODITY's Open Call #2 Campaign - BEFORE the OC launch

FOODITY_OC#2 Comms Tasks			
MONTH	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBLE	NOTES
BEFORE the OC launch			
1st half APRIL	Stakeholders database growth (external partners, NCPs, DIHs, women's associations, HE + H2020 projects, etc.)	AUS	SPECIFIC SEARCH SIAs
	Draft schedule of the OC info webinars	AUS + F6S	1st webinar - 13th of May week Matchmaking - 23rd of May 2nd webinar - 17th of June
	Define communication strategy + content calendar	AUS + F6S	
	Present the OC communication strategy at Biweekly	AUS	APRIL 16TH
	F6S pages	AUS + F6S	Review all OC2 FS6 pages: > F6S OC#2 > F6S SIAs > 1 per webinar > F6S Matchmaking collab event

FOODITY_OC#2 Comms Tasks			
MONTH	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBLE	NOTES
BEFORE the OC launch			
	Preparations Matchmaking	AUS	Meeting already held with Maja. Next steps: - Pitch doc stored in FOODITY to download - Blog announcement: Maja will send us a description template - SM posts and visuals : prepare a comms toolkit and joint calendar. FOODITY visuals and DRG4food copy. - Announcement launch date: beginning of April: sneak peek. Joint campaign about OCs, intro about a joint event. Stay tuned. - From mid-April (when we have a clearer view of the calls topics), we can start a more focused promotion on the webinar. Keep in mind the different CTAs we want to include in the campaign at each stage. - List of platforms, apart from the Food2030. SciFoodHealth, Sotelin factory. - Send the information to the people interested in our 1st calls, webinars and events.
2nd half APRIL	Make sure we have all OC info on type and number of applicants, budget, target audience, funding, benefits, activities, KPIs, metrics, etc.	AUS + F6S	Changes: OC#1 page + create OC#2 + Evaluators call update Draft OC page structure already with the designer
	Update FOODITY's website with the OC info + prepare: - Permanent links docs - Registration to info webinars - FAQs section-- questions where you can click to "expand" and then the answer shows. (*Track visits to the OC site + documents downloads)	AUS	Following same system as OC#1 Draft content - F6S add your input FAQs section - NEW!

FOODITY_OC#2 Comms Tasks			
MONTH	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBLE	NOTES
BEFORE the OC launch			
	Search for events and initiatives in which to participate, newsletters and event sites and relevant websites and SoMe channels/pages in which to include our OC information	ALL	In parallel with update of stakeholders collaboration framework. Do research with partners on what events are happening during the two months that the call is open that we can attend? This should be both in-person and online. Also search SFSN platform for events to potentially participate.
	Prepare a Communication Kit for the consortium including: - OC launch PR - Sample copys (for SoMe, email, newsletter, blog post) - Banners (adaptations) + animations highlighting key aspects of the OC - How/who/when to apply infographics	AUS	Following same system as OC#1 BUT 2 email templates: 1 for startups/SMEs 1 for SIAs/citizen engagement experts since the messaging will be very different
	1st webinar - announcement SoMe and attract participants (we need Zoom link) + start announcing matchmaking (for people to send pitch = 1st come 1st served / up to 12 pitching)	AUS	Disclaimer - submitting doesn't guarantee a spot / how to filter
	Make sure all the info to participate in the OC is ready: - <u>Website</u> (content, CTAs, mobile responsiveness) + connect to the application platform - <u>Open Call documents</u>	AUS	
	Start posting sneak-peak messages on FOODITY and consortium channels (prepare countdown visuals + copy)	AUS	When website is updated (latest 24 April)
	Start one-to-one emailing campaign to our stakeholders database - specific SIAs	AUS	START WITH SIAs - for website + matchmaking

FOODITY_OC#2 Comms Tasks			
MONTH	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBLE	NOTES
BEFORE the OC launch			
	Share database with partners and ask them to scout more target stakeholders	ALL	Following same system as OC#1
1st week May	Publish OC launch PR (in all our channels + Zenodo)	AUS	8th of May
	Send reminders to consortium to disseminate the materials in the Comms Kit	AUS	
	Keep announcing 1st webinar + matchmaking	AUS	
	DRG4FOOD podcast - May 13th	AUS	Plan BEFORE, DURING and AFTER announcement
	Start one-to-one emailing campaign to our stakeholders database asking to disseminate the OC + add us to their newsletters, website news sections, etc.	AUS	

3.4.2 During the Open Calls (Open Call #2)

Table 8. FOODITY's Open Call #2 Campaign - DURING the OC launch

FOODITY_OC#2 Comms Tasks - DURING the OC			
MONTH	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBLE	NOTES
MAY	(Launch day) Publish in participant portal – PO has to approve!	F6S	
	F6S launches its communication to its database	F6S	
	Announce in all channels & platforms + ask partners to do so in their internal and external, organisation and personal channels. Create visuals showcasing the application data.	ALL	
	Create a FOODITY newsletter for this announcement	AUS	
	Add call to publication platforms	AUS	SFSN platform, LSOS Collaboration Platform, etc
	Use FAQs to create specific content for SoMe . Same with “how to apply” infographics and other materials	AUS + F6S	
	F6S launches its communication to its database	F6S	
	1st webinar + record & use for further diss. (YouTube, website, SoMe, etc.)	AUS	Week 13th of May
	Prepare page and launch Evaluators Call	AUS	22nd May
	Prepare page and launch Experts Call	AUS	
	Announce 2nd webinar and open registration	AUS	18th of June
	Prepare countdown visuals + copy to publish on SoMe): 1 month left!	AUS	
	One-to-one emailing campaigns to our stakeholders database; - <u>Frequency</u> : from the week before the launch to the week after it is closed - <u>Topics</u> : Infodays + how to apply; OC (who, what, why, how, when); last call	AUS	
Check helpdesk - update FAQs / inform AUS	F6S		

FOODITY_OC#2 Comms Tasks - DURING the OC			
MONTH	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBLE	NOTES
JUNE	2nd webinar - Organise + Record + disseminate	AUS	17th of June
	Stakeholders + partners reminder: 2 weeks left, please keep disseminating!	AUS	
	Countdown 2 weeks left! 10 days left! 1 week left! 3 days left! 2 days left! 1 day left!	AUS	
	One-to-one emailing campaigns to our stakeholders database; - <u>Frequency</u> : from the week before the launch to the week after it is closed - <u>Topics</u> : Infodays + how to apply; OC (who, what, why, how, when); last call	AUS	
	Prepare page and launch Evaluators Call	AUS	
	Follow-up on D&C KPIs (compare with the reports from F6S) - Adjust targets depending on evolution	AUS	
JULY	Announce OC closure on all channels (also website). Stay tuned for results + approx. timeframe to expect results (F6S will send an automatic message from their platform, ask them to invite all submitted and draft applicants to follow FOODITY's channels + subscribe to its newsletter to be updated)	AUS + F6S	
	Evaluate results in terms of: followers, impressions, etc. = also monthly during call	AUS	
	Prepare infographic with results + article or PR	AUS	
	Share results in all channels	AUS	

3.4.3 After Open Call #2

Table 9. FOODITY's Open Call #2 Campaign - AFTER the OC launch

FOODITY_OC#2 Comms Tasks - AFTER the OC			
MONTH	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBLE	NOTES
SEP	Monitor and communicate the Impact of the funded projects: - Ask winners for permission to be featured in publications/interviews - Create content and a Comms Kit to share with partners and stakeholders.	AUS	Gather info from each winner - follow OC1 structure
	Announce winners in all channels (+schedule newsletter for this)	AUS	
	Comms Kit for winners	AUS	

3.5 Innovators Campaign

Another marketing campaign being implemented is the Innovators Campaign, addressed to **highlight the actions and impact of the projects being implemented by the 6 pilots approved in Open Call #1**. More actions will be added to this campaign as the 1st batch of pilots advance with their solutions. A second campaign will be implemented for the second batch.

Table 10. FOODITY's C&D Campaign - Open Call #1 winners

OPEN CALL #1 - Winners Campaign			
WHEN	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBLE	NOTES
JANUARY - MARCH	Request structured information from selected participants to be added to website	AUS	
	Interviews to winners	AUS	

OPEN CALL #1 - Winners Campaign			
WHEN	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBLE	NOTES
APRIL - JULY	News piece about support programme	AUS+SPL	Sploro already contacted for this
	Subpage for winners	AUS	After OC2 updates
	Publish 6 pieces on website + SoMe /1 per winner	AUS	4 Published
	Pilot 1 - CSE-TKAS	AUS	Post published in website + SoMe, video edited and uploaded
	Pilot 2 - FoodMarketMap	AUS	Post published in website + SoMe, video edited and uploaded
	Pilot 3 - STRADA	AUS	Video edited and uploaded
	Pilot 4 - DIAITA	AUS	Video edited and uploaded
	Pilot 5	AUS	Video edited and uploaded
Pilot 6	AUS	Video edited and uploaded	
AUGUST	Prepare materials for support programme campaign	AUS+SPL	Certificates, etc
SEPTEMBER	Publish results 1st phase support programme - 3 pilots going to 2nd phase	AUS+SPL	September
2025	Publish Star Award winner + interview	AUS	Jan 2025
2025	Succes Stories from 1st batch of pilots	AUS	

3.6 Citizen Awareness & Miscellanea Campaigns

Aside from the “bigger” campaigns already mentioned (different open calls, innovators) other campaigns are being implemented or are already being planned as next steps. Some details can be seen in the table hereunder.

Some other campaigns are started ad-hoc, depending on the developments and needs of the project.

Table 11. FOODITY's C&D Campaign - Miscellanea

MISCELLANEA C&D planning			
WHEN	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBLE	NOTES
APRIL - MAY	Datalake and dataU graphics	AUS + F6S + JIBE + SOF	
	Datalake logos	AUS + SOF	
	Citizen awareness campaign T5.3	ZSI + F6S + AUS	
	JIBE - Comms materials	AUS + JIBE	dataU
	Request for winners - regarding dataU	AUS + JIBE	Logo + messages
	Citizens workshop - extract learnings for campaign preparation	ZSI + F6S + AUS + SPL	Task 5.3 - Awareness raising campaign: - This campaign targets consumers and the broader public about the role of food and nutrition data and their role for environmentally friendly food systems. - With the results of WP1 + experiences of the pilot beneficiaries, AUS together with SPL, F6S, and ZSI will extract a campaign message and start a multichannel strategy to reach a broad audience.

MISCELLANEA C&D planning			
WHEN	ACTIONS	RESPONSIBLE	NOTES
JUNE	PhotoVoice Workshops Photo Book	ZSI + F6S + AUS + JIBE	Input sent by Maria for photo book: Overview on themes identified in the PhotoVoice Workshop in Vienna. Key messages Suggestions for wording for citizens as target group Photos participants have taken and linked with the specific topic.
JULY - AUGUST	PhotoVoice Workshops Photo Book - Lead search based on stakeholders' framework methodology	AUS	Events / Platforms / other recipients
	PhotoVoice Workshops Photo Book - Mailing & SoMe campaign	AUS	i.e. booklet + other potential materials
	Practice abstracts C&D	F6S	Prepare article and C&D
	Update follow-up events 2024	ALL	

It is worth mentioning the **awareness raising campaign**, targeting consumers and the broader public, about the role of food and nutrition data and their role for environmentally friendly food systems. This campaign, which will be active for the remainder of the project, follows a multichannel strategy to reach a broad audience with the results and learnings extracted from FOODITY and the funded pilots.

Some of the actions already implemented and related to this awareness campaign were more focused on the preparation of content and design of materials for setting up citizen awareness campaigns, as well as dissemination actions related to the PhotoVoice Workshops (which culminated with the creation of the Photo Book) and the Citizen Dialogues. The strategy for the awareness campaign is being further developed and more actions are planned for the upcoming months.

4 FOODITY exploitation and sustainability

This section addresses the FOODITY exploitation and sustainability measures as foreseen in Task 4.4 of the project. In this initial iteration, the focus has been on evaluating the exploitation and sustainability related to the initial project Key Exploitable Results (KERs) foreseen at the proposal stage. 2

4.1 Overview of the Key Exploitable Results

As initially foreseen in the GA, the following Key Exploitable Results (KERY) are identified:

1. **FOODITY pilot development program ['FOODITY fund']**, distributing 2M€ in funding to 12 teams, each receiving between 150,000k€ to 187,500€ in funding (main responsible: F6S).
2. **12 pilots of data-driven solutions** in the food and nutrition domain (main responsible: sub-grant beneficiaries).
3. **Library of AI-based software components** as building blocks for the food and nutrition pilots (main responsible: CERTH).
4. **Platform ['dataU platform']**, consisting of infrastructure and application components to guarantee citizen's data commercial mode for its exploitation (main responsible: JIBE).
5. **Data commons from data-driven solutions ['datalake']** in food and nutrition benefitting food value chain actors (main responsible: SOFTEAM)
6. **Engagement mechanism ['Citizen engagement mechanisms']** of over 200 citizens in expressing their concerns (main responsible: ZSI).

In this document, all KERs with exception to the 12 pilots of data-driven solutions are addressed, as these are still in development. The 12 pilots and their exploitation and sustainability measures will be included in the final iteration of this document.

To discuss the exploitation and sustainability measures of the five KERs, a common framework is proposed, which includes the use of two main tables. The first, included in this section, aims to provide a brief summary of the KER, including data that will be included on the EC portal for reporting purposes. The second, present in [Section 4.2](#), aims to provide more information on the KERs, based on what has been discussed and defined to date.

The tables below provide a brief summary of the five initial FOODITY KERs.

Table 12. KER#1: FOODITY pilot programme ('FOODITY fund')

KER#1: FOODITY pilot programme ('FOODITY fund')	
KER summary	The FOODITY Fund is a proposal for an innovation fund that builds and expands on the foundations established in the framework of FOODITY. It is a fund focused on funding applied research for data-driven innovation in the areas already targeted by FOODITY: sustainable food systems and nutrition.
Innovation overview	The FOODITY Fund innovates in the sense that it has a sectoral focus - sustainable food systems and nutrition - and aims to primarily fund SMEs (including earlier stage entities) that mainly focus on driving research into innovation in the mentioned areas. Also, collaborations with research-driven organisations (e.g. RTOs) are foreseen if there is a focus on applied research and a higher-end TRL. Furthermore, the fund encourages more data friendly and GDPR compliant solutions, taking advantage of the work developed in the framework of FOODITY.
KER type	SERV — Service (new or improved)
Target audience	Researchers Industry, business partners Investors Innovators Business accelerator providers
KER potential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High scientific potential • High societal potential • High technologic, business or economic potential
Market maturity	Emerging: growing demand, scarce supply
Related WP(s)/ Task(s)	Transversal to the project

Table 13. KER#2: Library of AI-based software components

KER#2: Library of AI-based software components	
KER summary	To facilitate the development of innovative applications in personalised nutrition and food retail, FOODITY introduced a set of five ready-made components. The components were created by CERTH and are directly related to various functions concerning dietary and wellbeing education, advice and support.
Innovation overview	Component #1 ("Food recognition from photo") and #3 ("Personalised nutrition plan"): The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms for automatic suggestions; Component #4 ("Personalised support for nutrition/physical activity") and #5 ("Nutrition and activity Ontology"): The use of Ontology for automatic advice provision; Component #2 ("Food product identification from photo"): N/A.

KER type	METH — Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)
Target audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Innovators
KER potential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Components #1-4: High scientific potential; High technologic, business or economic potential; • Component #2: N/A.
Market maturity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Component #1, 3, & 4: Emerging: growing demand, scarce supply. • Component #2 & 5: Mature: the market is already supplied with similar products.
Related WP(s)/ Task(s)	WP2

Table 14. KER#3: dataU platform

KER#3: dataU platform	
KER summary	DATAU is a solution for trustworthy, secure, large-scale data-sharing transactions.
Innovation overview	<p>The dataU allows citizens to manage and exercise their data rights according to GDPR and it allows software developers to include the dataU solution into their new applications to ensure GDPR compliance.</p> <p>Comparing services are created by i4trust² but dataU is specifically for selected types of data to be shared. i4Trust unleashes the potential of data sharing among different participants in multiple domains, allowing you to define cross-domain data value chains.</p>
KER type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PROD — Product (new or improved) • SERV — Service (new or improved) • INFRA — new or improved infrastructures or facilities
Target audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Industry, business partners • Investors • Citizens • End users (practitioners, farmers, etc.) • Research infrastructures
KER potential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High scientific potential • High societal potential (other than climate or environmental)

² https://i4trust.org/wp-content/uploads/i4Trust_DataSharingPlaybook.pdf

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High societal potential • High technologic, business or economic potential • High policy or regulatory potential
Market maturity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market creating: not existing but potential for the creation of a new market
Related WP(s)/ Task(s)	WP2: Task 2.1 and Task 2.2

Table 15. KER#4: data lake

KER#4: data lake	
KER summary	The FOODITY data lake serves as a centralised repository for storing and analysing large volumes of data related to food and nutrition domains. It provides stakeholders and researchers with access to diverse datasets while ensuring compliance with GDPR regulations.
Innovation overview	The FOODITY data lake introduces innovation by offering a centralised platform specifically tailored to the food and nutrition domain. It facilitates seamless collaboration among data providers, researchers, and citizens while prioritising data privacy and GDPR compliance.
KER type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PROD : The data lake platform itself, serving as a product that offers a centralised repository for storing and analysing data related to food and nutrition. • SERV : The service provided by the data lake platform, offering stakeholders access to diverse datasets and analytics tools including powerful advanced dashboards. • INFRA: The infrastructure supporting the data lake platform, including servers, databases, networking, and security measures.
Target audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data providers (manufacturers, nutritionists) • Researchers • Entrepreneurs and food producers • European citizens
KER potential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enables data sharing and collaboration • Facilitates research studies on food and nutrition • Empowers entrepreneurs with access to public data • Enhances transparency and understanding of food value chains
Market maturity	Market creating, The global data lake market size was valued at \$5.80 billion in 2022. The market is projected to grow from \$7.05 billion in 2023 to \$34.07 billion by 2030. More at:

	https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/data-lake-market-108761
Related WP(s)/ Task(s)	WP2: Task 2.3

Table 16. KER#5: Citizen engagement mechanisms

KER#5: Citizen engagement mechanisms	
KER summary	The first part of the PhotoVoice workshops is already finished and distributed to project partners, and also the citizen dialogue guide is available. The handbook will be improved and extended with experiences after finalisation of three citizen engagement processes.
Innovation overview	N/A
KER type	LEARN
Target audience	All
KER potential	N/A
Market maturity	N/A
Related WP(s)/ Task(s)	WP4, WP5

4.2 Detailed presentation of the KERs

4.2.1 FOODITY pilot development program ['FOODITY fund']

Table 17. KER#1: FOODITY pilot programme ('FOODITY fund') - DETAIL

KER#1: FOODITY pilot programme ('FOODITY fund')	
KER description and the problem it addresses	The FOODITY GA foresees the exploration of new funding possibilities and exit business models to finance the FOODITY acceleration programme. In this light, the definition of a 'FOODITY Fund' is proposed, which aims to fill the need of a food and nutrition specific funding programme that promotes research and innovation in these domains, particularly targets the role of data, and fosters multi-disciplinary collaboration.
Unique value proposition (UVP) and	The UVP of the FOODITY Fund is its sectoral focus - sustainable food systems and nutrition - and the aim to primarily fund SMEs (including earlier stage

KER#1: FOODITY pilot programme ('FOODITY fund')

<p>innovation</p>	<p>entities) that mainly focus on driving research into innovation in the mentioned areas. Furthermore, specific areas/ verticals will be defined, representing core topics with a high innovation potential, but with a natural risk that could be covered by the grant type mechanism. These topics will be identified in a later stage of this process, but a tentative list covers, for example: digital innovation in the food value chain, sustainable food chains (including production and distribution), sustainable nutrition recommendation systems, personal data sovereignty, and citizen empowerment in food systems.</p> <p>Also, collaborations with research-driven organisations (e.g. universities, RTOs) are foreseen if there is a focus on applied research and a higher-end TRL. Furthermore, the fund encourages more data friendly and GDPR compliant solutions, taking advantage of the work developed in the framework of FOODITY.</p> <p>At this stage, it is still being discussed if the FOODITY fund will be fully equity free (grants) or hybrid, with equity investments. While grant funding is more appealing to applicants, the possibility of having equity investments will possibly attract more investors to the fund.</p> <p>Furthermore, as the fund builds on the FOODITY project, there is an interest to also leverage the technological infrastructure of the project, namely the components, dataU and data lake, which are also FOODITY KER.</p> <p>Depending on the type of funding made available, the possibility of open-source requirements is to be considered. Therefore, any funding that comes from public resources will likely include some encouragement to <i>give back</i> to the community by making part of the work developed open source for further research and innovation.</p>
<p>Market Target audience and geography</p>	<p>At this stage, the main target audience for the FOODITY Fund are SMEs, including start-ups at most stages of their development (starting at pre-seed). This is a preferred target for the fund as it is expected to enable quicker delivery of results and innovation and less red tape often in place in higher education and RTOs.</p> <p>Still, RTOs are a potential target for the fund, particularly those with a proven commitment to collaborate with industry to deliver technological and social innovations and solutions.</p> <p>For both these targets, and particularly SMEs, their core domain should be technology, solutions, and services related to food and food systems and nutrition.</p> <p>With regard to the geographical landscape, the long-term objective is to be at a global level. To start, the fund would have a predominantly EU focus and gradually extend to other regions (e.g. Africa, where food system solutions</p>

KER#1: FOODITY pilot programme ('FOODITY fund')

	<p>could have particular value), and later worldwide. This is particularly important given the borderless economy of food systems, and the importing and exporting of practices, which merits the opportunity for entities across the globe to take advantage of the funds.</p>
<p>Market Early adopters</p>	<p>For this KER, early adopters should be understood as the first target of the fund. That said, these would be SMEs and select RTOs from the EU, tentatively EU Member States and a selection of countries currently associated with Horizon Europe.</p> <p>Moreover, another possibility of the early adopters could be a subset of SMEs, particularly micro or small enterprises, providing these with an opportunity to apply to funds with organisations at a similar level and with similar resources (compared to medium enterprises).</p>
<p>Market Competitors</p>	<p>For this KER, competitors should be understood as other funds or programmes that offer funding in similar target areas: food, food systems, and nutrition.</p> <p>There are currently several funds and programmes with opportunities in the mentioned areas, which have different objectives and rules. Examples of competitors to this fund are provided as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horizon Europe - Cluster 6: Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment. This cluster focuses on, among others, ensuring “food and nutrition security for all within planetary boundaries through knowledge, innovation and digitalisation in agriculture, fisheries, aquaculture and food systems.” One of the key areas of intervention of the cluster is food systems, and it aims to contribute to the objectives of the ‘Farm to Fork strategy’. Cluster 6 has been allocated approximately €9 billion for the full programme and approximately €897 million for the calls in the 2023 Work Programme. • European Circular Bioeconomy Fund (ECB). The ECBF is self-described as the “first venture capital fund exclusively dedicated to the (circular-) bioeconomy” and “aims to catalyze the transition towards a sustainable future.” The fund plans to invest €300 million in growth-stage companies with “high potential for innovation, favourable returns, and sustainable impact”. It has a geographical focus aligned with what is being conceptualised for the FOODITY Fund. • EIT Food. The EIT Food is self-described as Europe’s leading food innovation initiative, and a knowledge and innovation community dedicated to making food systems more sustainable. EIT Food provides access to multiple funding opportunities, but a place for

KER#1: FOODITY pilot programme ('FOODITY fund')	
	investors to also fund ideas. EIT Food aims to facilitate more than €350 million in investment funding to more than 800 companies.
Go-to-market Use model	<p>For this KER, use should be understood as how the FOODITY fund will be made available and known to its customers.</p> <p>Considering the initial focus on the EU region, preference will be given to EU platforms that promote such funds. Depending on the type of investments, the fund will also be published on those. As the FOODITY Fund stems from a EU project, it will also be a priority to associate the fund with the EU and have it alongside other EU funding mechanisms.</p>
Go-to-market Timing	<p>For this KER, timing should be understood as the timeline from initial ideation to possible first investments.</p> <p>Ideation is in progress as of the beginning of 2024 and as described in this document. It will continue to mature over the following months and up until the end of the project. By the end of the project, the objective is to have a defined framework and strategy for the fund, including specific details and data related with the fund type (e.g. grants, investments, venture capital), target (start-ups, and at what stage, SMEs, RTOs), the geographical focus, duration of the investment (if this is considered an option to pursue), specific verticals or areas of intervention, governance of the fund, and other relevant requirements.</p> <p>It will then be necessary to identify other funds and organisations willing to be associated with or invest in the fund, understand their conditions and specific requirements. To the extent possible, the FOODITY project would target securing initial letters of intent from such entities that could then be explored by the FOODITY partners or other entities interested in first managing this fund.</p> <p>The full timing from initial inception to the first granting of funds is not possible to define at this moment, but could take a minimum 1-2 years to secure commitments, define the final structure of the fund, and rules for funding and investment.</p>
Go-to-market IPR background & foreground	<i>N/A for this KER.</i>
IP protection plan	<i>N/A for this KER.</i>
Current TRL (M18)	<i>N/A for this KER.</i>
Target TRL (M36)	<i>N/A for this KER.</i>

KER#1: FOODITY pilot programme ('FOODITY fund')	
Joint exploitation intentions	<p>For this KER, joint exploitation should be understood as agreements between partners to jointly drive this initiative.</p> <p>At this stage, no agreements are in place and will be discussed in the second half of the project.</p>
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	<p>The main short to medium-term actions is to continue the ideation of the FOODITY fund and to further define its preliminary framework and strategy. This also includes possibly identifying initial letters of intent from interested investment funds and other organisations willing to participate in the FOODITY fund. By the end of the project, the FOODITY fund should, at least:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have its framework defined (i.e. target, geography, types of funds/ investments, requirements). • Strategy for roll-out and capturing funds/ investors. • Letters of commitment from interested funds and entities.

4.2.2 Library of AI-based software components

Table 18. KER#2: Library of AI-based software components - DETAIL

KER#2: Library of AI-based software components	
KER description and the problem it addresses	<p>A library of digital components for data-driven food and nutrition solutions including software, ontology, and reasoner.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Component #1 'Food recognition from photo': An AI model that automatically recognises food depicted in a photo. Receives as input a photo of food, analyses the photo, and provides as output a probability for each element in a specified list of foods (food titles), to be the depicted food. • Component #2 'Food product identification from photo': A python script that automatically identifies a food product barcode from a photo of the barcode and uses this information to retrieve product information from free online product databases. Automatically identifies a food product barcode from a photo of the barcode, e.g., photo of a food product, and uses this information to retrieve food product information from free online databases. • Component #3 'Personalised nutrition plan': A software component that recommends a weekly nutrition plan tailored to an individual's profile. Receives as input a database of dishes, meals, and user profiles and provides as output a weekly nutrition plan tailored to each user's profile. • Component #4 'Personalised support for nutrition/physical activity': A knowledge-based, decision support system (DSS) in the form of Software as a Service (SaaS), that prioritises foods/ physical activities according to the personal medical conditions, needs, and preferences of an individual. The system prioritises foods/ physical activities (e.g., in a meal plan, in a restaurant menu, in an activity plan), based on

KER#2: Library of AI-based software components

	<p>whether they are advised given a user's personal medical conditions, needs and preferences. In addition, it filters out - or can potentially issue an alert - over given foods/ physical activities, when they are not medically advised or even potentially hazardous for a given user.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Component #5 'Nutrition and activity Ontology': An ontology of nutritional, medical, and lifestyle factors that affect healthy living. It comprises an amalgamation of European guidelines relevant to nutrition and well-being. It also includes experts' evidence-based knowledge, pertaining to foods and their relation to nutrients as well as to foods/ physical activities and their well-being consequences, restrictions, and specific goals relevant to user conditions. It can be used to coalesce nutritional, medical, behavioural and lifestyle indicators with potential dietary and physical activity directives. • your 'customers' - have).
Unique value proposition (UVP) and innovation	N/A
Market Target audience and geography	Food system actors, e.g., producers, retailers, distributors, etc., mostly SMEs, but also for large companies that are developing their own software and components. Also, academia/ RTO/ education actors in the context of research projects or lab work.
Market Early adopters	N/A
Market Competitors	N/A
Go-to-market Use model	<p>Possible use models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology transfer • Licence agreement • Contract research • Research publications
Go-to-market Timing	Components are ready.
Go-to-market IPR background & foreground	The KER is based on extending past work (background) of partner CERTH. Specific restrictions for exploitation were agreed in the FOODITY CA: "Access to the background for Exploitation is not provided by right. Access may be provided by licence".
IP protection plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Component #1 'Food recognition from photo'</i> The component is provided under the following licence: "Food recognition from photo" © 2023 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is licensed under CC BY-NC 4.0. • <i>Component #2 'Food product identification from photo'</i>

KER#2: Library of AI-based software components

	<p>The component is provided under the following marking: "Food product identification from photo" © 2023 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is marked with CC0 1.0.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Component #3 'Personalised nutrition plan' The component is provided under the following licence: "Personalised nutrition plan" © 2023 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is licensed under CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 • Component #4 'Personalised support for nutrition/physical activity' The component is provided under the following licence: "Personalised support for nutrition/physical activity" © 2023 by Dorothea Tsatsou, Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is licensed under GNU Lesser General Public License v3.0. • Component #5 'Nutrition and activity Ontology' The component is provided under the following licence: The Nutrition & Activity Ontology (NAct) © 2021 by Dorothea Tsatsou, Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0
Current TRL (M18)	TRL 6 – Technology demonstrated in relevant environment
Target TRL (M36)	TRL 6 – Technology demonstrated in relevant environment
Joint exploitation intentions	None
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	N/A

4.2.3 Platform ['dataU platform']

Table 19. KER#3: dataU platform - DETAIL

KER#3: dataU platform	
KER description and the problem it addresses	<p>DataU is positioned as the data-sharing and management platform across the EU. DataU presents a lightweight, distributed technical solution to a global challenge. It aims to increase trust in organisations by ensuring control, transparency and visibility for the data owners. Regardless of whether DataU is integrated in a B2B, B2B2C or B2G2C environment, the technology ensures data-security remains at the forefront.</p> <p>In a B2B scenario, DataU facilitates large scale, cross-border data-transfers between various stakeholders along the industrial value chain, by allowing data-owners to manage, control, secure and transmit data. As such, dataU can become an essential building block in various industry 4.0 solutions. Anchored by secure, scalable architecture, and carefully chosen technical</p>

KER#3: dataU platform	
	<p>solutions, DataU also serves as a GDPR-compliant platform not only for private companies, but also for public administrations, allowing them to build smart cities or dedicated government-citizen services and applications.</p> <p>Designed based on practical use-cases and with EU public administrations in mind, the custom-built architecture ensures DataU is the optimal solution when it comes to data security.</p> <p>Straightforward to implement and flexible to run, DataU has modest operational requirements, with optional service models to support interested bodies. Furthermore, the platform's unique characteristics make it possible to leverage standardised access to create new services at an organisational-level or even platform-wide.</p>
Unique value proposition (UVP) and innovation	<p>DataU is a GDPR-compliance application, designed for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Millions of private users, sharing data with the central services of governmental organisations in an H2020 project: PoSeiD-on. • Millions of software developers that can connect to dataU to make their new service GDPR compliant: developed in this HE FOODITY project. • Data sharing network for industrial value chains: DataU supports cross-border data-sharing alongside the industrial value chain for Industry 4.0. • Loyalty points, designed for: millions of private users, collecting and spending loyalty points at various retailers. • A platform to manage data-sharing towards smart services, designed for: smart health services for private citizens and smart energy services for private homes.
Market Target audience and geography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governments that want to digitise their services to citizens. • Software developers that want to build services that need to be GDPR compliant or where a data owner needs to manage the sharing of sensitive data.
Market Early adopters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Currently used in EU projects. • Commercial early adapters: not identified yet.
Market Competitors	<p>I4trust has been identified as a potential competing service. It is believed that the DataU service can be more specific for managing personal and sensitive data and explicitly manage consents for sharing personal and sensitive data and perhaps even add value for i4trust. It is planned to contact I4trust to see a possible collaboration.</p>
Go-to-market Use model	<p>The following routes are considered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DataU as a development platform: DataU source-code is available for ICT-companies/ departments or research groups that want to develop further services on top. • DataU as a Service: DataU as a data sharing and permission network service, to connect your own e-services and make it available to your network or community of users. Easy Plug and Play instructions, API

KER#3: dataU platform	
	<p>and examples are supplied to the developers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DataU customer specific solutions: if the two mentioned options are not suitable, we can begin a developmental project to design & build a customer specific solution.
Go-to-market Timing	Exact planning is still needed to be done.
Go-to-market IPR background & foreground	The concept of DataU is background knowledge and the use for governmental services. The specific use of DataU for software developers is developed in FOODITY and can be seen as foreground knowledge. Background and foreground are both treated as JIBE owned IPR.
IP protection plan	To be determined.
Current TRL (M18)	TRL 5/6 as dataU solutions are being tested with real developers from the FOODITY project.
Target TRL (M36)	TRL 6/7 as a dataU production version is being developed that is suitable for automated and more easy connecting and that can be scaled. This version will be tested and validated in the second part of the project.
Joint exploitation intentions	Not addressed at the moment.
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	Not addressed at the moment.

4.2.4 Data commons from data-driven solutions ['data lake']

The FOODITY data lake platform serves as a centralised repository for storing, analysing, and sharing data related to food and nutrition. The platform comprises two websites: one for data providers and another for European citizens and researchers. Built on the ELK stack, leveraging Elasticsearch, Logstash, and Kibana, the platform offers advanced data storage, analysis, and visualisation capabilities. This technological foundation provides scalability, flexibility, and robust performance, ensuring efficient data management and exploration.

Table 20. KER#4: data lake - DETAIL

KER#4: data laked	
KER description and the problem it addresses	The KER addresses the need for a centralised data repository in the food and nutrition domain, catering to various stakeholders such as researchers, citizens, entrepreneurs, and food producers. It aims to provide easy access to valuable insights while ensuring compliance with GDPR regulations.
Unique value	The FOODITY data lake platform offers a user-friendly interface, robust

KER#4: data laked	
proposition (UVP) and innovation	privacy protection, and scalability. It innovatively connects data providers and researchers, facilitating collaboration and knowledge exchange. Its competitive advantages lie in its comprehensive data storage capabilities, efficient data search, and GDPR compliance.
Market Target audience and geography	<p>The target audience of the FOODITY data lake platform includes a diverse range of stakeholders within the food and nutrition domain, such as:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Food producers and manufacturers: These entities can benefit from the platform's data storage and analysis capabilities to optimize production processes, monitor product quality, and identify market trends. 2. Researchers and academia: Researchers in the fields of nutrition, public health, and food science can leverage the platform to access valuable datasets for academic studies, epidemiological research, and policy development. 3. Government agencies and regulatory bodies: Entities responsible for food safety regulations and public health policies can use the platform to gather insights from food-related data, monitor compliance, and make informed decisions. 4. Healthcare professionals: Dietitians, nutritionists, and healthcare providers can utilise the platform to access nutritional information, track dietary trends, and develop personalised dietary plans for patients. 5. Entrepreneurs and startups: Individuals and startups seeking to innovate in the food industry can explore datasets on consumer preferences, market trends, and ingredient sourcing to develop new products and services.
Market Early adopters	<p>The early adopters of the data lake platform are likely to be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Large food corporations: Companies with extensive data resources and a strong focus on innovation are likely to be early adopters. They may include multinational food corporations seeking to optimise supply chain processes, enhance product development, and gain competitive insights. ● Research institutions: Academic institutions and research organisations involved in food and nutrition studies may be early adopters, using the platform to access comprehensive datasets for research purposes and collaboration.
Market Competitors	<p>Competitors to the FOODITY DataLake platform may include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Existing data aggregation platforms: Generic data aggregation platforms that offer similar data storage and analysis capabilities across various domains may pose competition. These platforms may have established user bases and partnerships within their respective industries. 2. Traditional research methods: Traditional research methods, such as surveys, focus groups, and manual data collection, may be considered competitors, particularly among users who are less

KER#4: data laked	
	<p>familiar with data-driven approaches.</p> <p>Strengths of the FOODITY data lake platform, in contrast to competitors, stem from its domain-specific focus on food and nutrition. This specialisation ensures a more tailored and relevant dataset, addressing the unique needs of stakeholders within this industry. Furthermore, its user-friendly interface facilitates efficient data exploration and analysis, while its scalability accommodates varying data volumes and user demands. Integration with advanced technologies like the ELK stack enhances its analytical capabilities, providing users with robust tools for deriving actionable insights. However, potential weaknesses include the initial learning curve for users unfamiliar with data analytics platforms and the imperative challenges associated with ensuring data privacy and security compliance in a sensitive domain such as food and nutrition</p>
Go-to-market Use model	<p>The FOODITY data lake platform will be made available to customers through a service-based use model. Users, including data providers, researchers, and European citizens, will access the platform through dedicated websites tailored to their specific needs. Data providers will utilise the platform to submit and manage their datasets, while researchers and citizens will access the platform to explore, analyse, and utilise the available data for research, decision-making, and public information purposes. This service-based model ensures easy accessibility and usability for all stakeholders involved in the food and nutrition domain.</p>
Go-to-market Timing	<p>The time to market for the data lake platform is expected to be immediate upon the conclusion of the project. Once the project concludes, the platform will be fully operational and available for use by stakeholders, researchers, data providers, and European citizens interested in accessing and analysing food and nutrition-related data. Therefore, there will be no delay between the project's end and the platform's usability.</p>
Go-to-market IPR background & foreground	<p>The data lake platform is a result of completely new developments (foreground) initiated within the project. It is not based on extending past work but rather on innovative solutions and technologies developed by SOFTEAM. No existing platforms or technologies were directly leveraged in the development of the data lake, making it a novel and unique offering within the market landscape.</p>
IP protection plan	<p>SOFTEAM plans to protect its intellectual property through appropriate means. We intend to explore options such as patents or copyright protection for the unique aspects of the platform's architecture, algorithms, and user interface design. Additionally, we will consider implementing licensing agreements to govern the use of the platform by external parties, ensuring that our intellectual property rights are respected while still enabling collaboration and innovation within the food and nutrition research community.</p>
Current TRL (M18)	<p>At M18, the FOODITY data lake platform is expected to be at a TRL 5. The</p>

KER#4: data laked	
	platform has undergone initial development and testing, with the basic functionality implemented and demonstrated in a controlled environment. However, further refinement and optimization are still required to achieve full usability and scalability.
Target TRL (M36)	By the end of the project at M36, the goal is to elevate the platform to a TRL of 8 to 9. At this stage, the platform will have been fully developed, tested, and validated in real-world settings. It will be operational and available for widespread use by stakeholders in the food and nutrition research community.
Joint exploitation intentions	SOFTEAM does not plan to jointly exploit the KER with other partners. The development and exploitation of the FOODITY data lake platform will be solely undertaken by SOFTEAM.
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Publication strategy: SOFTEAM plans to publish articles and white papers showcasing the capabilities and benefits of the FOODITY data lake platform in relevant scientific publications. Participation in events: SOFTEAM intends to participate in conferences, workshops, and industry events to showcase the platform to potential users and stakeholders, fostering collaboration and partnerships. User feedback integration: Continuous feedback collection from users will be integrated into the platform's development roadmap to ensure that it meets the evolving needs of its users and maximises its utility and impact. Documentation and support: Comprehensive documentation and user support services will be provided to facilitate seamless onboarding and usage of the platform, ensuring a positive user experience and maximising adoption rates.

4.2.5 Engagement mechanism ['Citizen engagement mechanisms']

Many technical developments occur without involving the end users, particularly in such a complex field such as food and nutrition data. Although vast amounts of data are collected from users, they are rarely or minimally included in development or decision-making processes. Their needs and concerns are not surveyed, and their suggestions and ideas are not considered. In the FOODITY project, we have made it our specific mission to work closely with end users and citizens. Our goal is to employ tools that enable us to connect with them and hear their voices and exchange opinions.

Table 21. KER#5: Citizen engagement mechanisms - DETAIL

KER#5: Citizen engagement mechanisms	
KER description and the problem it	Based on the scientific analysis of three citizen engagement processes at three locations (Vienna, Sofia, Coimbra), a public handbook for participation

KER#5: Citizen engagement mechanisms	
addresses	is being developed. The results will be compiled in the planned deliverable D5.1. Subsequently, they will be presented in a clear and concise format and summarised into a ready-to-go document. This handbook will be available as a compact PDF document for free download. The handbook addresses how complex issues such as data privacy and data sovereignty can be discussed with citizens in an accessible manner and how co-creative development processes can be conducted.
Unique value proposition (UVP) and innovation	Guides for citizen engagement processes do already exist. The stand-alone aspect of this handbook is that it is based on real life experiences and examples within the complex food (data) system and is adaptable to other fields.
Market Target audience and geography	The target audience of this document includes all those interested in starting or facilitating a participation process in complex fields such as food and nutrition data, as well as decision-makers or consultants who wish to commission such processes. The free download option via different distribution channels will allow access from all over the world.
Market Early adopters	<i>N/A</i>
Market Competitors	<i>N/A</i>
Go-to-market Use model	<i>N/A</i>
Go-to-market Timing	<i>N/A</i>
Go-to-market IPR background & foreground	<i>N/A</i>
IP protection plan	The handbook will follow creative commons principles and will be openly accessible.
Current TRL (M18)	<i>N/A</i>
Target TRL (M36)	<i>N/A</i>
Joint exploitation intentions	<i>N/A</i>
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	Insights of all FOODITY hub citizen engagement activities (Austria, Bulgaria, Portugal) will be analysed and published in a scientific paper.

4.3 Individual exploitation plans

The sections below present for each FOODITY partner the initial individual exploitation plans, which cover the KERs presented above and other results developed/ to be developed in the project.

4.3.1 F6S

Table 22. Individual exploitation plan FS6 - FOODITY Fund [KER #1]

Result name	FOODITY Fund [KER #1]
Type of result	SERV — Service (new or improved)
Delivery date	December 2025 (M36)
Overview	As described above: The 'FOODITY Fund' will fill the need of a food and nutrition specific funding programme that promotes research and innovation in these domains, particularly targets the role of data, and fosters multi-disciplinary collaboration.
Innovation overview	As described above: The FOODITY Fund innovates in the sense that it has a sectoral focus - sustainable food systems and nutrition - and aims to primarily fund SMEs (including earlier stage entities) that mainly focus on driving research into innovation in the mentioned areas. Also, collaborations with research-driven organisations (e.g. RTOs) are foreseen if there is a focus on applied research and a higher-end TRL. Furthermore, the fund encourages more data friendly and GDPR compliant solutions, taking advantage of the work developed in the framework of FOODITY.
Target audience/ market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Industry, business partners • Investors • Innovators • Business accelerator providers
Partners involved and tasks	F6S with the support of multiple partners.
License	N/A
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	The KER is currently in an ideation phase, focused on defining the FOODITY Fund framework and strategy. This is expected to be completed by the end of the project. Furthermore, it is planned to collect letters of intent from other funds and investors interested in delivering this KER.

Table 23. Individual exploitation plan FS6 - Dataset of entities and contacts collected through the FOODITY open calls (funding, experts, and mentors)

Result name	Dataset of entities and contacts collected through the FOODITY open calls (funding, experts, and mentors)
Type of result	SERV — Service (new or improved) <i>From the perspective that they are contacts, some new, that can benefit from other programmes or opportunities (services) offered by F6S</i>
Delivery date	December 2025 (M36) <i>Date by when the databases will no longer receive inputs, but will be used.</i>
Overview	As of 15 June 2024, the dataset includes more than 600 entries. These include organisations that have applied to the FOODITY Open Call #1 or Open Call #2 , individuals that have applied to the first and second experts expressions of interest, or the call for mentors . This excludes the dataset of more than 700 individuals that have signed up to the six online events organised by FOODITY or co-organised with DRG4FOOD.
Innovation overview	No particular innovation associated with this result.
Target audience/ market	From a perspective of the offer, these individuals and entities will be provided with information about services that are of interest to them (e.g. funding, mentoring) coming from projects managed by F6S.
Partners involved and tasks	F6S, AUS, SPL
License	N/A
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	Datasets will be used as required to deliver services.

4.3.2 AUSTRALO

Table 24. Individual exploitation plan AUS - Dataset of contacts collected through the FOODITY marketing and mailing campaigns

Result name	Dataset of entities and contacts collected through the FOODITY marketing and mailing campaigns (funding, experts, and mentors)
Type of result	SERV — Service (new) <i>These network of contacts can be included in the offers coming from other AUS campaigns searching for experts, evaluators, relators, collaborators or participants in open calls, events or training programmes.</i>
Delivery date	December 2025 (M36)
Overview	As of 28 June 2024, the dataset includes more than 1,300 entries. These include EDIHs, SMEs and startups, EU associations, cluster, industry representatives, social innovation actors, universities, RTOs, etc.
Innovation overview	No particular innovation associated with this result.
Target audience/ market	These contacts can be provided with information about services that are of interest to them (e.g. funding, connections, synergies, etc) coming from projects participated by AUS.
Partners involved and tasks	AUS with support of other partners (Task 5.5 – Stakeholder Collaboration Framework)
License	N/A
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	Not addressed at the moment

4.3.3 CERTH

Table 25. Individual exploitation plan CERTH - Library of AI-based software components (KER #2)

Result name	Library of AI-based software components (KER #2)
Type of result	SCI — Scientific discovery, model, theory
Delivery date	Delivered.
Overview	Digital components related to various functions concerning dietary and wellbeing education, advice and support.
Innovation overview	N/A
Target audience/ market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Industry, business partners • Innovators • Education/ training organisations/ learners
Partners involved and tasks	CERTH
License	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Component #1 'Food recognition from photo' The component is provided under the following licence: "Food recognition from photo" © 2023 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is licensed under CC BY-NC 4.0. • Component #2 'Food product identification from photo' The component is provided under the following marking: "Food product identification from photo" © 2023 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is marked with CC0 1.0. • Component #3 'Personalised nutrition plan' The component is provided under the following licence: "Personalised nutrition plan" © 2023 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is licensed under CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 • Component #4 'Personalised support for nutrition/physical activity' The component is provided under the following licence: "Personalised support for nutrition/physical activity" © 2023 by Dorothea Tsatsou, Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology

Result name	Library of AI-based software components (KER #2)
	<p>Hellas (CERTH) is licensed under GNU Lesser General Public License v3.0.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Component #5 'Nutrition and activity Ontology' The component is provided under the following licence: The Nutrition & Activity Ontology (NAct) © 2021 by Dorothea Tsatsou, Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0.
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	<p>The components were provided to innovators through the FOODITY Open Call and are currently being integrated in their innovations by those that were successfully selected as FOODITY beneficiaries.</p>

4.3.4 JIBE

Table 26. Individual exploitation plan JIBE - dataU [KER #3]

Result name	dataU [KER #3]
Type of result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PROD — Product (new or improved) • SERV — Service (new or improved) • INFRA — new or improved infrastructures or facilities
Delivery date	December 2023 (M12): development platform for dataU December 2025 (M36): production version dataU
Overview	<p>DATAU is a solution for trustworthy, secure, large-scale data-sharing transactions. This KER allows citizens to manage and exercise their data rights according to GDPR and it allows software developers to include the dataU solution into their new applications to ensure GDPR compliance.</p> <p>Comparing services are created by i4trust but dataU is specifically for selected types of data to be shared. i4Trust unleashes the potential of data sharing among different participants in multiple domains, allowing you to define cross-domain data value chains.</p>
Innovation overview	I4trust has been identified as a potential competing service. It is considered that the dataU service can be more specific for managing personal and sensitive data and explicitly manage consents for sharing personal and sensitive data and perhaps even add value for i4trust. Plans to contact I4trust for a collaboration are being considered.
Target audience/ market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data providers (manufacturers, nutritionists) • Researchers • Entrepreneurs and food producers • European citizens
Partners involved and tasks	N/A
License	Not addressed at the moment
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	Not addressed at the moment

4.3.5 SOFTEAM

Table 27. Individual exploitation plan SOFTEAM - FOODITY Data Lake [KER #4]

Result name	FOODITY Data Lake Platform
Type of result	SERV
Delivery date	December 2025 (M36)
Overview	The FOODITY data lake platform is a centralised repository designed to store, analyse, and share vast volumes of data related to food and nutrition domains. It facilitates collaboration among stakeholders, including researchers, citizens, entrepreneurs, and food producers. With a user-friendly interface, it enables easy share, exploration and extraction of datasets. Compliant with GDPR regulations, it ensures privacy protection while offering valuable insights for various applications such as analytics, and research.
Innovation overview	The platform introduces innovation by providing a comprehensive solution tailored to the specific needs of the food industry. Its user-friendly interface, robust privacy controls, and scalable architecture differentiate it from existing products, offering an integrated platform for data management and analysis.
Target audience/ market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food producers and manufacturers • Entrepreneurs in the food industry • Researchers and academics in nutrition and food science • Policy makers and regulatory bodies in food safety and nutrition
Partners involved and tasks	SOFTEAM
License	Commercial
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market analysis to identify potential users and their specific needs. • Engage research consortia for collaborative integration. • Present at academic conferences and workshops. • Publish articles showcasing platform capabilities. • Collaborate with research institutions for joint studies. • Partner with academic journals for dissemination. • Participate in research webinars and forums. • Continuous improvement of the platform based on user feedback and market trends.

4.3.6 SPLORO

Table 28. Individual exploitation plan SPLORO - FOODITY Programme

Result name	FOODITY Programme
Type of result	SERV
Delivery date	December 2025 (M36)
Overview	The FOODITY Programme ensures scalability and exploitability by standardised processes, integrating technology and fostering partnerships. Using a model of training innovators, it empowers them to replicate the methodology in the future. Continuous improvement based on data collected monthly optimises results, while a franchise model allows for rapid expansion with minimal investment. Regular feedback loops ensure relevance and effectiveness, promoting sustainable growth and impact.
Innovation overview	The FOODITY Programme includes a strategic approach oriented to maximise the benefits from the coaching process with topics that covers many needs from different areas. It is set in a way that the methodology could be sold to other projects or teams related to the innovation in the food and nutrition fields, but not only restricted to them. Moreover, this methodology can be exploited in other topics due to its scalability and the open vision of the topics covered.
Target audience/ market	Innovators
Partners involved and tasks	SPLORO (WP4)
License	Commercial
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	A Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) was created, divided into topics, completed with all the recordings and materials. The access to this space could be sold asking for a payment in return for a certificate when all sessions are completed. Use the Sploro Platform as an open online repository where everyone can contribute. It serves as a database for e-lessons on each topic, workshops, experts, coaches, and mentor's database.

4.3.7 ZSI

Table 29. Individual exploitation plan ZSI - D5.2. Handbook on citizen empowerment process

Result name	D5.2. Handbook on citizen empowerment process
Type of result	LEARN
Delivery date	December 2024 (M24)
Overview	Public handbook with consolidated experiences and guidance for citizen empowerment processes.
Innovation overview	N/A
Target audience/ market	All audiences
Partners involved and tasks	Partners JIBE, F6S, AUS
License	Creative commons
Actions (planned/ implemented) towards exploitation	Promotion through FOODITY channels (e.g. website, social media)

5 Next Steps

The main aim of the Dissemination and Communication strategy in FOODITY is to **ensure that the project results and opportunities are accessible to stakeholders and that the knowledge gained and benefits are effectively shared** with them. As the project progresses into its second half, efforts will be intensified to ensure that all stakeholders are well-informed about the project's outcomes and activities.

During this phase, FOODITY will reinforce various activities:

- Participation in **events, conferences, and workshops**: FOODITY will actively engage in events to present its results and will engage with stakeholders to plan joint activities in this regard.
- **Scientific publications**: CERTH is awaiting the publication of their paper submitted to the Nutrients (MDPI) Journal, while other partners are planning to get published in the coming months, such as ZSI and SOFTEAM.
- **Engagement with the ecosystem**: Specific efforts will be made to scout new potential targets for the project, grow the current database, and make sure to reach women as well as other less represented collectives; the FOODITY team will work on strengthening the engagement with other EU projects and related initiatives, enhancing joint dissemination activities, including promotional campaigns, events, workshops, and papers.
- **Email campaigns**: FOODITY will utilise email campaigns to inform stakeholders about key events, Open Calls, and share key advancements and technologies.
- **Newsletters**: project newsletters will continue to be released, supplemented by flash news on LinkedIn for significant achievements.
- **Online presence**:
 - Website: In the coming period, we will focus our marketing and communication strategies on giving visibility to the results of this first call and promoting the second call to considerably increase the website's traffic and make FOODITY known to as many people as possible.
 - Social media: FOODITY will dedicate specific efforts to reach a community of 2,500 online followers and attract subscribers to its newsletter. Social media campaigns and blogs will increasingly focus on promoting the project's technical accomplishments, as well as the results of the work with the Open Calls beneficiaries.
- New **multimedia materials and visuals** will be created to attract attention to the developments of the project, such as videos, short clips, creativities, etc.
- **Open Calls**: Based on the learning obtained during the first Open Call of the project, the Communication and Dissemination Strategy will be updated to reach the best applicants for the second call, as well as to support the funded innovators in their journey.

- **Next steps for exploitation and sustainability:**

- Given the different types of KERs presented and others that may be identified in the second half of the project, as well as the status of each KER, next steps in terms of exploitation and sustainability analysis vary.
- KERs #1, #3 and #4 offer the most opportunity for further exploration. Specific activities that will be considered for these KERs include:
 - Provision of more information on market and competition
 - SWOT Analysis
 - Business Canvas, where applicable
 - Business and revenue model, where applicable
 - Detail of activities that have supported exploitation of KER (applicable to all KERs)
 - Exploitation roadmaps

6 Conclusions

This report serves as the mid-project update on FOODITY's Dissemination and Communication strategy, offering insights into the project's progress after 18 months of operation. Over this period, FOODITY has achieved significant milestones, including the establishment of a unique visual identity, the development of primary digital communication channels, and the execution of collaborative initiatives in publication and promotion. These efforts have resulted in the creation of a cohesive brand identity for the project, enhancing its online presence and fostering engagement within an expanding community.

The **Communication and Dissemination** strategy of FOODITY has evolved continuously to adapt to the project's dynamic nature, requiring ongoing collaboration from the consortium. This flexibility ensured that outreach materials, channels, and tools were refined to reflect the project's progress and notable achievements. As the project advances, the emphasis will shift towards more targeted dissemination activities, particularly in the technical/scientific domain and support to the selected Pilots. Consequently, efforts in fieldwork and networking will intensify in the later stages of the project, leveraging digital channels to maximise reach and visibility.

With regard to **exploitation**, an initial assessment and description of the project's key exploitable results has been made, including their value, target audience, protection plan, and others. For a selection of these, more details will be provided over the coming period including key steps to ensure their exploitation or sustainability, as applicable. Furthermore, details about the exploitation plans of the 12 sub-granted projects will be provided.

ANNEX A: FOODITY site for Open Call #1

Do you have the next big digital idea to empower citizens to make healthier food choices and create more sustainable food systems?

Apply to our Open Call #1 for your chance to join our FOODITY programme, get funded up to €187.500, and receive training and support to develop your solution!

We are running a **1M€** pilot development programme for creating **6 data-driven solutions** to drive innovation in food and nutrition while putting the power of personal data use back into the hands of citizens.

Call closed

The Open Call #1 offer

 12 MONTHS PROGRAMME with services for pilot development			
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The Open Call #1 challenges

Our first open call will accept submissions to develop solutions focusing on one or more of three areas or an open challenge:

What to consider before submitting your application:

- The open call will accept proposed solutions currently between **TRL 4 and 6**, but capable of scaling up to **TRL 7**.
- All pilots must focus on **social innovation** and promote **citizen engagement**.

Phases of the FOODITY programme

We will develop our pilot development programme in three phases. The first one will focus on implementing the pilot projects. The second one on maximising their impact. The programme will end with an award ceremony where the winning pilot projects will benefit from an additional **€7,500**.

Our data storage management system

Enabling citizens to become aware of their data is central to our visions, as it allows them to control how it is used and where it is stored.

We have developed a **data architecture** to protect and properly store user data, which we will require the pilot projects to use. This datalake will store the data (apart from users' personal data, the management of which will be the responsibility of the pilots concerned), and our **data_U** software will process and manage it.

The selected FOODITY innovators will learn how to properly use this data architecture through **training and mentoring**, as well as deepen their understanding of the **ethics of data management**, among other technical topics.

The training will also cover **citizen participation methods**, as pilots must involve end-users from start to finish. **Mentoring support**, especially in the second phase, will focus on business matters, from innovation strategy to product development. In addition, pilots can request support in specific areas to ensure TRL advancement.

What's in it for you? Our value-added services

Our programme beneficiaries – the FOODITY innovators – will receive a wide range of value-added services:

FINANCIAL SUPPORT
 Up to 187.500€ per beneficiary.

- ACCESS TO TECHNOLOGY**
and technical support to develop their solutions.
- EXPERT MENTORING**
Advice on business development: from marketing and sales to financing, innovation strategy or sustainability.
- GROUP COACHING**
Including mutual exchange between the open call beneficiaries.
- TECHNICAL TRAINING**
Training on relevant technical, business, and legal issues.

Who are we looking for? The **FOODITY** innovators

To arrive at tangible and impactful solutions, the teams that develop them must be diverse. That is why we are looking for organisations with both **technical** and **social innovation expertise**, as well as **citizen engagement knowledge**.

Applicants can submit proposals led by an SME/startup and partner with other 2 or 3 entities that are a mix of for-profit and non-profit organisations.

Small or Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) and startups

developing solutions for data-driven innovation in personalised nutrition, sustainable food systems and shopping experiences.

Social innovation actors (SIAs)

providing new practices aiming at citizen empowerment and proposing concrete actions for data sovereignty, as well as associations representing consumers' interest in health and nutrition

Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) and universities

working on advancing the state-of-the-art and addressing the challenges around data-driven innovation for health and nutrition, as well as mechanisms to preserve citizens' sovereignty over their personal data in health and nutrition solutions.

Training organisations

oriented to the food industry, such as culinary or nutrition schools, and interested in teaching and experimenting with the power of data for innovation and competitiveness in food production and diet planning.

Apply now!

The open call will run from **5 September to 8 November 2023 (17.00 CET)**. All applications will then be evaluated by external experts.

Applications must be submitted in English through the [F6S platform](#).

In addition, applicants must be based in an EU or [Horizon Europe-associated country](#). Watch our info webinars to learn the keys to this open call and find out if it is for you.

FOODITY Open Call 1: Webinar 1

Watch later Share

FOODITY Open Call #1 Webinar #1

Learn about our 1st Open Call to fund data-driven solutions for food and nutrition!

13 September 2023

Watch on YouTube

Funded by the European Union

FOODITY Open Call 1 - Webinar 2

Watch later Share

FOODITY Open Call #1 Webinar #2

Discover the keys to our Open Call for data-driven solutions in food and nutrition

18 October 2023

Watch on YouTube

Funded by the European Union

How to find the right partners?

Are you interested in participating but haven't found the right partners? If you are an SME looking for a social innovation partner, you can start by referring to this [global interactive map](#) which provides information on verified social innovation actors (not all listed actors may fit your needs, and other entities that are not listed may also qualify). At FOODITY, we will support match-making opportunities on our [F&S page](#) and coordinate networking events to help you find the right partners to advance your solutions.

Stay tuned to our channels!

[Subscribe to our newsletter](#) and [follow us on social media](#) to learn about our match-making opportunities, networking events and info webinars.

Our evaluation criteria

CONCEPT & RESEARCH CHALLENGES

Show how your proposed solution is aligned with the FOODITY vision and is innovative.
Provide objectives and address challenges associated with citizens' data rights and GDPR regulations.

IMPACT & INNOVATION POTENTIAL

Describe expected results from the pilot programme and connect them to the [FOODITY vision](#), as well as [FOOD 2030](#) goals.
Provide both a qualitative and quantitative overview of expected long-term impact and measures to exploit results post-project.

DATA RIGHTS & CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT

Provide a provisional plan for safeguarding user data and an overview of how data will be stored and managed.
Describe citizen engagement activities for phases I and II, including examples of proposed activities and level of engagement.

TEAM & IMPLEMENTATION

Describe the work plan and propose a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).
Describe the team's expertise, technical knowledge, social innovation capacity in relation to citizen engagement and respect for gender balance.

Open Call #1 documents

Make sure to read our Open Call #1 documents carefully before submitting your application!

[Open Call overview](#)

[Guidelines for applicants](#)

[FAQs](#)

[Documents and templates](#)

Any questions?

Write to us at opencalls@foodity.eu

Subscribe to our newsletter

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Figure 21. FOODITY's site for Open Call #1

ANNEX B: FOODITY site for Open Call #2

Do you have the next big digital idea to empower citizens to make healthier food choices and create more sustainable food systems?

Apply to our Open Call #2 for your chance to join our FOODITY programme, get funded up to €187,500, and receive training and support to develop your solution!

We are running a **1M€** pilot development programme for creating **6 data-driven solutions** to drive innovation in food and nutrition while putting the power of personal data use back into the hands of citizens.

[Apply now](#)

We are accepting submissions for Open Call #2
Apply by 10 July 2024 (17.00 CET)!

21 Days
22 Hours
06 Minutes

The Open Call #2 offer

#2 OPEN CALL	6 PILOTS	1M€ FUNDING	12 MONTHS PROGRAMME
launching on 8 May and closing on 10 July 2024	to be developed by the selected applicants	and financial support of up to €187,500 per beneficiary	with services for pilot development

The Open Call #2 themes

Our second open call will accept submissions to develop solutions focusing on one of the themes or an open challenge:

What to consider before submitting your application:

- The open call accepts proposals for solutions with a minimum entry level of 4 - 6 TRL and currently up to TRL 7 (preferred but not mandatory)
- All pilots must focus on **social innovation** and include **citizen engagement** activities in their work plan.

Phases of the FOODITY programme

We will develop our pilot development programme in three phases. The first one will focus on implementing the pilot projects. The second one on maximising their impact. The programme will end with an award ceremony where the winning pilot projects will benefit from an additional **€7,500**.

Our data storage management system

Enabling citizens to become aware of their data is central to our vision, as it allows them to control how it is used and where it is stored. We have developed a **data management architecture** to protect and properly store data, which we will require the selected FOODITY innovators to use. The FOODITY **datalake** will store data (apart from users' personal data, the management of which will be the responsibility of the pilots concerned), and the **dataU** will process and manage it.

dataU

The FOODITY dataU is a GDPR-compliant, cloud-based, distributed platform for secure data sharing. It allows full control over data, including with whom it is shared and for how long.

The service can be used to share data between citizens (data owners) and third-party services (data processors) or between two companies in accordance with their non-disclosure agreements.

datalake

The FOODITY datalake provides a centralised repository that makes data accessible for stakeholders and researchers while allowing them to perform different analyses – from temporal trends to user behaviour.

All data entered adheres to GDPR compliance, ensuring the protection of citizens and providing valuable information for applications in areas such as business intelligence and analytics.

Selected FOODITY innovators will be given training and mentoring on how to use our unique data management architecture.

What's in it for you? Our value-added services

Our programme beneficiaries – the FOODITY innovators – will receive a wide range of value-added services:

FINANCIAL SUPPORT

Up to €187.500 per beneficiary.

ACCESS TO TECHNOLOGY

and technical support to develop their solutions.

EXPERT MENTORING

Advice on business development: from marketing and sales to financing, innovation strategy or sustainability.

GROUP COACHING

Including mutual exchange between the open call beneficiaries.

TECHNICAL TRAINING

Training on relevant technical, business, and legal issues.

Who are we looking for? The FOODITY innovators

To arrive at tangible and impactful solutions, the teams that develop them must be diverse. That is why we are looking for organisations with both **technical** and **social innovation expertise**, as well as **citizen engagement knowledge**.

Applicants can submit proposals led by an SME/startup and partner with other 2 or 3 entities that are a mix of for-profit and non-profit organisations.

Small or Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) and startups

developing solutions for data-driven innovation in personalised nutrition, sustainable food systems and shopping experiences.

Social innovation actors (SIAs)

providing new practices aiming at citizen empowerment and proposing concrete actions for data sovereignty, as well as associations representing consumers' interest in health and nutrition

Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) and universities

working on advancing the state-of-the-art and addressing the challenges around data-driven innovation for health and nutrition, as well as mechanisms to preserve citizens' sovereignty over their personal data in health and nutrition solutions.

Training organisations

oriented to the food industry, such as culinary or nutrition schools, and interested in teaching and experimenting with the power of data for innovation and competitiveness in food production and diet planning.

Apply now!

The open call will run from 8 May to 10 July 2024 (17.00 CET). External experts will then evaluate all applications.

Applications must be submitted in English through the [F6S platform](#).

In addition, applicants must be based in an EU or [Horizon Europe-associated country](#).

[Apply now](#)

Sign up for our info webinars and events to learn the keys to this open call and find out if it is for you!

- **Info webinar 1**
16 May 2024, 3:00 - 4:15pm CET [Watch it now](#)
- **DRG4FOOD & FOODITY Matchmaking Event**
23 May 2024, 3:00 - 4:30pm CET [Register now](#)
- **Info webinar 2**
18 June 2024, 3:00 - 4:00pm CET [Register now](#)

How to find the right partners?

Are you interested in participating but haven't found the right partners?

If you are an SME looking for a social innovation partner, you can start by referring to this [global interactive map](#) which provides information on verified social innovation actors (not all listed actors may fit your needs, and other entities that are not listed may also qualify).

At FOODITY, we will support **matchmaking opportunities** to help you find the right partners to advance your solutions.

Don't miss the matchmaking event we will celebrate on 23 May (3:00 - 4:30 pm) together with our sister project, DRG4FOOD!

[Register now](#)

Are you a Social Innovation Actor (SIA)?

- A non-profit organisation that provides new practices aimed at citizen empowerment and proposes concrete actions for data sovereignty.
- An association representing consumers' interests in health and nutrition.

Fill in the form below with your organisation's key information. We will feature it on our website so other organisations can contact you to collaborate on a joint proposal.

[Fill in the form](#)

Stay tuned to our channels!

[Subscribe to our newsletter](#) and [follow us on social media \(LinkedIn, Twitter, Mastodon and YouTube\)](#) to learn about our info webinars and matchmaking opportunities.

Our evaluation criteria

CONCEPT & RESEARCH CHALLENGES

Show how your proposed solution is aligned with the FOODITY vision and is innovative. Provide objectives and address challenges associated with citizens' data rights and GDPR regulations.

IMPACT & INNOVATION POTENTIAL

Describe expected results from the pilot programme and connect them to the [FOODITY vision](#), as well as [FOOD 2030](#) goals. Provide both a qualitative and quantitative overview of expected long-term impact and measures to exploit results post-project.

DATA RIGHTS & CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT

Provide a provisional plan for safeguarding user data and an overview of how data will be stored and managed. Describe citizen engagement activities for phases I and II, including examples of proposed activities and level of engagement.

TEAM & IMPLEMENTATION

Describe the work plan and propose a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Describe the team's expertise, technical knowledge, social innovation capacity in relation to citizen engagement and respect for gender balance.

Open Call #2 documents

Make sure to read our Open Call #2 documents carefully before submitting your application!

- [Overview](#)
- [Guidelines for applicants](#)
- [Technical Annex](#)
- [Proposal template](#)
- [Full documentation kit](#)

FAQs

Eligibility

1. Do partners have to be from different countries?	-
No, partners can be from the same country.	
2. Can a corporation form part of a consortium?	+
3. Are universities eligible?	+
4. Are companies required to be VAT registered?	+
5. Is Hungary eligible?	+

Budget

6. Are there expectations regarding budget allocation per partner within a consortium?	-
No, there are no requirements on budget allocation within a given consortium. It must be decided internally on an appropriate budget per partner while keeping in mind that costs must be logical and justified.	
7. How are indirect costs calculated (refer to "Financial Eligibility" Section 3.2 from the Guidelines)?	+
8. Is subcontracting allowed?	+

Technical

9. Are there exceptions to the TRL minimum and maximum at the application phase/start of the pilot programme?	-
No, the minimum TRL is 4 and any proposals that fall under this minimum will be automatically deemed ineligible. Any applications in which the TRL is above 6 will also be automatically deemed ineligible.	
10. Is it a requirement to reach TRL 7 at the end of the pilot programme?	+
11. Are the components provided by the FOODITY consortium open access?	+
12. How can we work with the components if we haven't seen them before and when will they be accessible?	+
13. What will happen to the data collected and stored during the pilot programme, as well as the datalake post-project?	+
14. Who owns the data that is stored in the datalake?	+
15. Is data encryption allowed in the dataU?	+
16. Can my company's own data platform be connected with FOODITY's datalake?	+

Other

17. How long does it take to submit an application?	-
There is no standard amount of time a given application takes to complete. It depends on how far developed the proposed solution is, how well the Guidelines have been understood, as well as the evaluation criteria, and the applicant's experience with EU funds. It is advised to start as soon as possible to avoid rushing through the proposal.	

Any questions?

Write to us at opencalls@foodity.eu

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Figure 22. FOODITY's site for Open Call #2

ANNEX C: FOODITY site for Evaluators Call

At FOODITY, we are running our [Open Call #2](#) to fund projects focused on developing data-driven solutions in food and nutrition with respect to citizens' data sovereignty and aim to establish a pool of experts to support us in evaluating the applications we receive.

The pool of experts established through this expression of interest (Eoi) will consist of individuals with knowledge in **social innovation, citizen engagement, data and technologies, and food and nutrition** topics addressed within FOODITY. We will select them through an open process to ensure independence and transparency in evaluating the applications to the open call.

Want to join our pool of experts? Apply by **12 June 2024!**

CALL CLOSED

The reimbursement for your participation

Evaluators will be reimbursed for their time and effort based on the number of applications evaluated (minimum number to be agreed), with each application corresponding to a value of **€50** considering all the services required.

Who are we looking for?

We are looking for experts with knowledge in various domains, particularly:

- Social innovation and citizen engagement
- Data management and data quality
- Technology and app/service development, and TRL advancement
- Marketing and business scaling technologies (app/service development)
- A demonstrated understanding of food systems and solutions in our three Open Call #2 themes (shopping experiences, education, and services)
- Experience in evaluating EU-funded projects is considered an asset

Experts will be assessed based on their professional experience and expertise in the mentioned areas. Experience in proposal evaluation that covers relevant FOODITY topics will not be considered as expertise in the given subject. Applicants are expected to prove at least three years of experience in the specific field/subject area of claimed expertise.

What are the benefits of being an evaluator?

LEARN ABOUT EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES
in the food and nutrition domains, as well as advancements in citizen data sovereignty.

PARTICIPATE IN THE SELECTION
of innovative data-driven projects.

CONNECT WITH INNOVATIVE STARTUPS
SMEs, researchers and non-profit stakeholders.

What services are required?

The services to be provided will be carried out remotely and will consist of evaluating a selection of applications submitted to FOODITY Open Call #2.

The evaluation process involves analysing several proposals, participating in consensus meetings, and validating evaluation reports.

Evaluators will be required to sign a non-conflict of interest declaration and a contract with FOODITY before being accepted to evaluate any application.

[Download the contract template](#)

*Document subject to changes

Important Notice

Please note that this expression of interest to participate in the FOODITY Open Calls evaluation as an external expert is NOT binding and does NOT represent any commitment to the FOODITY project.

The selection of experts to support the evaluation of the FOODITY Open Calls will be carried out at a later stage, depending on the number of applications received, their origin, and the domains they address. The selection will also consider the experts' origin, affiliations, expertise and the balance between various criteria (e.g. gender, background, affiliation type, expertise, etc.). Furthermore, the project is obliged to frequently change experts that support the evaluation of applications.

[FOODITY Open Call #2](#)

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Figure 23. FOODITY's site for Evaluators Call

ANNEX D: FOODITY site for Experts Call

Are you experienced in supporting entrepreneurs in their initial phases and have a taste for innovative solutions in the food and nutrition sector?

We invite you to join us as an expert for our Services Programme.

This is your chance to be part of a dynamic team that helps shape the future of food and nutrition through data-driven innovation.

Stay tuned for our next call to join the FOODITY Services Programme.

[Subscribe to our newsletter](#)

About the FOODITY Services Programme

Through the FOODITY Services Programme, we will provide technical and business support to the selected beneficiaries in our **Open Calls** (our FOODITY innovators) to help them reach their goals and maximise their impact.

This is a specialised **12-month** support programme that will involve experts offering **value-added services** to our FOODITY innovators to ensure the success of their projects. Activities will range from tailored training to coaching webinars and other resources to strengthen their skills and knowledge.

This close collaboration between FOODITY experts and innovators will enable them to receive the support they need to overcome the challenges presented by the programme and reach their full potential through their projects.

The Service phases

As an expert, you will be part of the two phases of the Programme:

Phase 1: Pilot development

Phase 1 will last **9 months** and will be delivered to 6 projects.

It is divided into 3 stages:

- **Stage A:** Specification and design (1.5 Months)
- **Stage B:** Implementation (6 months)
- **Stage C:** Validation and verification (1.5 months)

Phase 2: Pilot testing

Phase 2 is focused on impact maximisation and will last **3 months**.

It will be delivered to the 3 top projects.

They will be helped with the pilot testing, impact maximisation and business sustainability measures.

Who are we looking for?

We are looking for experts with proven knowledge in various areas.

Phase 1: Pilot development

- Product development
- Business strategy
- Business modelling
- Marketing and sales
- Legal training on European citizens data rights
- Financing
- Innovation strategy
- Decentralised technologies, sustainability, and gender
- Pitch deck

Phase 2: Pilot testing

- Impact maximisation measures
- Business sustainability measures
- Results exploitation

In-depth knowledge of food systems and sustainability and experience in supporting participants in EU-funded projects will be a strong asset.

Selection will be based on your professional experience, expertise in the above areas and previous involvement in mentoring proposals submitted to EU and FSTP (Financial Support for Third Parties) programmes.

Services required and remuneration

The main objective of this Services Programme is to facilitate the progress and development of the FOODITY innovator's projects by providing them with personalised support and guidance.

Phase 1 Services

Experts will offer domain-specific knowledge and deliver a **monthly joint webinar** during Phase 1 of the programme. They will have a **one-to-one session** with the programme participants to solve questions, receive feedback on the tasks set and evaluate the knowledge they have acquired on the different topics. They will also **assist** the participants in refining business models, strategising effectively, accelerating solutions into the market, and bridging the gap between theory and practice.

Phase 2 Services

Individual coaching sessions will be provided to the top 3 projects to ensure their pilot implementation, impact maximisation and exploitation of their business project.

Summary of services and remuneration

Period	Services	Remuneration
Phase 1 (Jan-Sept 2024)	Per selected month 1h online webinar 6 individual online sessions Evaluation meeting with the organiser	800€/month VAT excl.
Phase 2 (Oct-Dec 2024)	3h coaching x 3 projects 3 evaluation meetings with the organiser	900€ in total VAT excl.

[Foodity Open Calls](#)

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Figure 24. FOODITY's site for Experts Call

ANNEX E: FOODITY site for Materials & Resources

Citizen engagement and empowerment

Download

PhotoVoice Workshops Photo Book

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Subscribe

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Figure 25. FOODITY's site for Materials and Resources

ANNEX F: FOODITY Open Call #2 Communication & Dissemination Toolkit

Help us reach food innovators to apply for FOODITY Open Call #2

Open from 8 May to 10 July 2024 (17.00 CET)

Welcome to the FOODITY Open Call #2 Communications Toolkit, your one-stop shop for resources that you can use to promote the [FOODITY Open Call #2](#), aimed at funding six innovative data-driven solutions in food and nutrition that respect users' right to sovereignty over their personal data.

Please help spread the word and attract potential applicants! Share this opportunity with anyone you think may be interested and promote it within your network and through your communication channels to help us reach as many people as possible.

Thanks for your cooperation. Your support is vital to build better food systems, together.

Need something you can't find here? Contact us at foodity@australo.org

Useful links

[FOODITY OC #2 Website](#)

[Application Site \(F6S\)](#)

[SIAs Site \(F6S\)](#)

[Info Webinar #1](#)

[Matchmaking Event](#)

[Info Webinar #2](#)

Keys to FOODITY Open Call #2

- **Goal:** To support innovative **data-driven solutions** that will contribute to developing sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty.
- **Value-added services:** Selected beneficiaries will receive funding (up to €187,500), tailored expert mentoring and training, group coaching, and technical support to scale their products and services over 12 months.
- **Who are we looking for?** Startups/SMEs, social innovators, research organisations and universities, and training entities (organisations with technical, social innovation, and citizen engagement expertise).
- We'll accept submissions to develop solutions focusing on one of our **themes** — **shopping experiences, education or services** — or an open challenge. Solutions must focus on **social innovation** and include **citizen engagement** activities in their work plan.

Application deadline: 10 July 2024 (17.00 CET)

[Learn more](#)

Communication materials

Press release

This Press Release announces the launch of FOODITY Open Call #2, including the necessary links to apply and access all relevant information. Feel free to edit it according to your needs. We recommend adapting the language to your audience for a wider reach and strongly suggest you publish it on your website and share it with your media database.

*it is also uploaded to our [Zenodo repository](#).

Funded by the European Union

FOODITY

Press Release
8 May 2024

FOODITY launches its second open call to fund data-driven solutions for food and nutrition

The EU-funded project FOODITY will fund six data-driven solutions to reshape food systems while championing data sovereignty. These innovations will enable citizens to contribute to healthier, more sustainable food systems.

FOODITY's €1M pilot development programme beneficiaries will receive up to €187,500, tailored expert mentoring, and technical support to advance their products and services over 12 months.

Organisations wishing to participate in the FOODITY programme can apply to this open call from 8 May to 10 July 2024 to get the support they need to scale their solutions.

FOODITY (FOOD and nutriTION Data-driven innovation respectful of citizen's Data Sovereignty) is pleased to announce the launch of its Open Call #2 as part of a wider mission to develop a dynamic ecosystem of digital solutions for food and nutrition that respect citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty in Europe.

This EU-funded initiative has a programme for SMEs/startups, social innovation actors, researchers, and training organisations developing solutions for data-driven

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Visuals

[Launch video](#)

Horizontal banners

Flyer

Apply to FOODITY Open Call #2

Do you have the next big digital idea to empower citizens to make healthier food choices and create more sustainable food systems?

OPEN CALL #2
closing on **10 July**
2024

6 PILOTS
to be developed

€1M FUNDING
support of up to
€187.500

12 MONTHS
support
programme

We are looking for

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Sample texts

Use these sample texts to promote the Open Call on your online channels (social media, newsletters, mailings, etc.) and take our tips into account!

Share FOODITY Open Call #2 online

We have launched our [FOODITY Open Call #2](#)! It will be **open from 8 May to 10 July 2024 (17.00 CET)**. You can use these materials to promote it among your network and help us bring this exciting opportunity to as many food innovators and data sovereignty enthusiasts as possible. Feel free to edit them according to your needs (we recommend adapting the language to your audience for a wider reach).

*Let us know your questions or suggestions at foodity@australo.org

> [Download the Open Call #2 Press Release and visuals HERE.](#)

[Sample texts](#)

[Social media](#)

For any questions or suggestions, feel free to contact us at foodity@australo.org

Figure 26. FOODITY's Open Call #2 Communication & Dissemination Toolkit